

Toward an Ontology for EA modeling and EA Model Quality

Jan A. H. Schoonderbeek

Promotor: Prof. Dr. Henderik A. Proper

Co-promotor: Marco A. Dumont, MSc.

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Executive Summary

Researchers of enterprise architecture modeling usually introduce their own lexicon, accepting (often implicitly) the accompanying ontological commitments. Similarly, practitioners of enterprise architecture modeling implicitly commit to different ontologies, resulting in models that have an uncertain ontological standing. This is because for the subject domain of enterprise architecture models (as opposed to the content of such models), no single ontology has gained major traction.

As a result, studies into aspects of enterprise architecture models, such as “model quality” and “return on modeling effort”, are fragmented, and cannot readily be compared or combined. And enterprise architecture modelers lack practical guidance with which to create enterprise architecture models that are of sufficient quality.

These problems can be addressed when a suitable applied ontology becomes available to the researchers, as well as the practitioners of enterprise architecture modeling. An applied ontology represent structured knowledge about a particular subject domain. It allows for study into, and reasoning about, its subject domain.

This thesis proposes a comprehensive applied ontology, specifically geared to enterprise architecture modeling. This ontology is labeled EAMOn, which stands for **Enterprise Architecture Model Ontology**.

EAMOn is derived from the existing scientific understanding of what a domain model is, and supplemented with theories of knowledge and of language. It encompasses a theory of modeling, while clarifying concepts such as “enterprise architecture model”, and introduces novel concepts such as “model audience” and “model objective”. Furthermore, the relevant interrelations between these different concepts are identified and defined. The resulting applied ontology for enterprise architecture models is then captured in an OntoUML model, thus showing it to be consistent with a suitable foundational ontology, namely Unified Foundational Ontology (UFO).

An initial test of practical validity of EAMOn, and an example of the value of its use in the practice of enterprise architecture modeling, is also included. EAMOn is used to uncover and dissect the modeling process, so its quality influences can be discussed. Following this, a number of practical modeling guidelines are drafted that promote quality by addressing the identified quality influences. Some of these modeling guidelines are reflected in similar guidelines in the existing professional body of knowledge for enterprise architecture. Other modeling guidelines appear to be novel. This serves to underline the practical value that EAMOn brings to the practice of enterprise architecture modeling.

Keywords

Enterprise architecture — Enterprise architecture model — Enterprise architecture modeling — Applied ontology — EAMOn

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On a precursor and on a sibling of this thesis

In 2020 I wrote a bachelor thesis on quality attributes for enterprise architecture models ([Schoonderbeek, 2020](#)). This thesis forms a follow-up, and hopefully provides a foundation that will enable future research, including my own, to obtain better results.

Partial results of the presented thesis have been submitted as a paper to the Journal of Software and Systems Modeling (SoSyM) for the Theme Section on “Trends in Enterprise Architecture Management Research”¹. Like this thesis, this paper has the title “Toward an Ontology for EA Modeling and EA Model Quality”, for which I am listed as the first author, and my promotor as coauthor. At the time this thesis is being finished, mid May 2023, this paper is still under review, and accordingly has not yet been accepted for publication.

On the tools that helped create this thesis

This thesis has been created in [Overleaf](#), an online \LaTeX editor. Latex is very daunting at first, presenting you with a pretty steep learning curve. But if you have a programmer’s mindset, then Latex is not only very handy and predictable, but also rewarding and fun. Plus: having Latex automatically handle all the references, citations, tables et cetera better than standard text editors do, which frees up the mind for the important stuff – the content. Furthermore, the cloud nature of the Overleaf implementation also makes cooperation with promotors and reviewers really easy.

Some illustrations have been made using [Microsoft PowerPoint](#); others with [Visual Paradigm](#) with the [OntoUML plugin](#). For some additional very advanced (ahem) image manipulation I used [Microsoft Paint](#). References were managed in [Clarivate EndNote](#), and stored on my private [Nextcloud](#) environment. Over many days and nights I kept myself powered using a Philips [Senseo Select CSA240/60](#) and several thousand coffee pads of type Regular, Strong, Extra Strong, Gold, and Gold Intense. This coffee machine is an upgrade over the HD7825 used for my bachelor thesis – I hope it shows.

Some remarks on the use of language and of specific words

In this thesis I will discuss enterprise architecture modeling and products, as well as the individuals that create and work with those products. As I am mindful of the power and impact of language, I have chosen to make use of the “singular they”² to promote gender-fair use of language. Thus, if you read “the EA modeler themself”, then this is not a spelling error.

This thesis is also full of technical terms, for which professionals in the field employ standard abbreviations. As an example: enterprise architecture is almost always abbreviated to EA. These abbreviations have been collected in section [Acronyms](#) (page 58). For the convenience of readers who browse this the-

¹The journal is found online [at this link](#), and the Call for Papers can, at the time of writing, be found [here](#).

²See for instance www.scribbr.com/nouns-and-pronouns/third-person-pronouns

sis, I have made sure that in every chapter, every acronym is written out in full the first time it appears in that chapter. Furthermore, even though I use acronyms all throughout this thesis, I have chosen to *not* do that in formal definitions, on the expectation that this will make the use of these definitions somewhat easier for the more casual or hurried reader.

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CHAPTER 1

Introduction

1.1 The problem of enterprise architecture model quality

This thesis is about [Enterprise Architecture \(EA\)](#) modeling and about [Enterprise Architecture Models \(EAMs\)](#). These are activities and products that play an important role in the field of EA ([International Organization for Standardization, 2022a](#); [Lankhorst et al., 2017](#); [Sandkuhl et al., 2014](#); [The Open Group, 2022a](#); [2022c](#); [Timm et al., 2017](#)).

When an organization requires change, it is up to the professionals in the field of EA to provide advice to decision makers on how to structure the organization and its different systems to enable this change, as well as guiding the implementation parties ([Lankhorst et al., 2017](#), ch.1). To that end, enterprise architects capture different architectures, such as baseline and target architectures, in EAMs. These models are underpinning many of the architects' professional products and services ([Lankhorst et al., 2017](#), ch.3-4).

Considering the important role that EAMs play in EA, one would expect a large volume of scientific literature covering EAMs and their quality. And in some areas of EAM, such work does exist – for example [Krogstie \(2016\)](#) who investigates quality in Business Process Models. It is certainly the case that much work has been done on the quality of *visualization* of EAMs ([Zhou et al., 2020](#)).

But despite the examples given above, there is a dearth of *scientific underpinning* for determining the quality of EAMs as a whole, as noted by e.g. [Niemi and Pekkola \(2013\)](#) and [Timm et al. \(2017\)](#). This also holds for the broader category of conceptual models, as noted by e.g. [Lindland et al. \(1994\)](#) and [Nelson et al. \(2011\)](#). And the value of a model *per se* is equally difficult to establish ([Guizzardi & Proper, 2021](#)).

The problem of EAM quality can succinctly be put as follows: outside of visualization, there is little theory on what constitutes model quality, how one could determine the quality of a model, or how one could obtain sufficient quality in the creation of a model.

And this scarcity of underpinning in the scientific literature extends to the professional body of knowledge as well. Notwithstanding works such as [Lankhorst et al. \(2017, ch.7\)](#), little scientifically founded *practical guidance* is available to create EAMs of sufficient quality, as I previously noted in [Schoonderbeek \(2020\)](#). As an illustration, a [search on Google Scholar](#) combining the three terms "practical guidance", "modeling", and "enterprise architecture" (executed on 5-5-2022, including the quotation marks) returned 305 results. Of these, none had as its main topic the practical guidance for *EA modeling* itself.

Consequently, most of the practical guidance available to EA modelers is based largely or entirely on the opinion of its writer. That guidance may actually be sound, and the quality of the results therefore sufficient (maybe even excellent), but without scientific underpinning and an objective standard for EAM quality, there is no way to tell such material apart from other works that do not lead to sufficient EAM quality.

Some practical problems that arise from this lack of scientific underpinning for EA modeling are:

- An EAM may be of insufficient quality to contribute to an organization’s decision making process for change initiatives, but practitioners of EA have no objective way to determine this. As practitioners of EA use these EAMs to support the decision makers, the quality of the outcome of the decision making process may suffer. To put that more bluntly: business decisions on change may be wrong because of bad EAMs.
- Not knowing what makes an EAM “good” means we cannot tell when to stop improving the model. But if an EAM is developed beyond the point of “good enough”, then every bit of that additional work diminishes the [Return on Modeling Effort \(RoME\)](#) ([Proper & Guizzardi, 2022](#)) for that EAM.
- Not knowing what influences model quality makes it hard to teach EA modeling to (aspiring or practicing) EA modelers.

More research into EAM quality is clearly needed, and this thesis sets out to provide a solid foundation for such research.

1.2 An ontology for researching enterprise architecture model quality

Any type of scientific research requires a suitable conceptual framework. Such a framework is expected to consist of the following three components ([Berman & Smyth, 2015](#)):

- Epistemology – *why* is this research required or desired;
- Ontology – *what* is it that is being researched;
- Methodology – *how* will the research be conducted.

Scientific research into EAM quality is in no way exempt of the requirement of a conceptual framework ([Recker & Niehaves, 2008](#)), and consequentially also requires these three components.

For EAM quality, the *why* is outlined in section 1.1 above. *How* to perform research is generally well understood by researchers already, and well documented in works such as Bell et al. ([2022](#)). In this thesis I will therefore focus on the remaining item of the list, the *what*: the ontology.

“Applied ontology is a branch of applied philosophy using philosophical ideas and methods from ontology in order to contribute to a more adequate presentation of the results of scientific research” ([Applied Ontology – An Introduction, 2013](#), p.21)

“An ontology is a conceptual model of (a fragment of) an observed reality; it is, in essence, a repository of interlinked concepts pertaining to a given application domain.” ([De Nicola & Missikoff, 2016](#), p.79)

“An ontology specifies a rich description of the

- terminology, concepts, nomenclature;
- relationships among and between concepts and individuals; and
- sentences distinguishing concepts, refining definitions and relationships (constraints, restrictions, regular expressions)

relevant to a particular domain or area of interest” ([Kendall & McGuinness, 2019](#), pp.2-3)

There are several *foundational ontologies* that are suitable to investigate certain aspects of the world ([Guizzardi et al., 2022](#)). One such foundational ontologies is explicitly geared towards conceptual models. This is the [Unified Foundational Ontology \(UFO\)](#) ([Guizzardi, 2005](#)). This ontology is foundational, so it does not provide the specific terms and relations to fulfill the requirements of investigating a specific domain. For that, a *domain* or *applied* ontology is required ([Applied Ontology – An Introduction, 2013](#), ch.1). Such an applied ontology would build out of a foundation ontology, in order to capture the essentials of its respective domain.

Despite its relevance to research into EAM quality, no suitable applied ontology for EA modeling and EAM quality readily presents itself:

“... we identify a lack of work regarding quality assessment of enterprise architecture models in general and frameworks or methods on that account in particular.” (Timm et al., 2017, p.14)

Many terms that are directly or indirectly involved with EAM quality have no definition that is widely agreed upon in the communities of researchers, nor of EA practitioners. Even the principal terms *EAM*, and *model* itself, are not well defined. As an illustration, consider the systematic literature review by De Meyer and Claes (De Meyer & Claes, 2018) for one subdomain of EAMs, namely business process models. This review presents 42 relevant secondary studies, containing 39 different quality dimensions and 21 quality metrics. But notably these studies did not agree, nor converge, on any single definition of process model quality, nor of model quality itself. Or consider *ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2022(E)* (International Organization for Standardization, 2022a), a standard for software architecture descriptions that is well referenced by EA frameworks such as *The Open Group Architecture Framework (TOGAF)* (The Open Group, 2022d) as the conceptual model for enterprise architecture descriptions in general, and consequentially also for EAMs. While acknowledging the activity of modeling, this standard omits the definition of *model* (EA, architecture, or otherwise) altogether; nor does it define the activity of *modeling*.

As a further complication, polysemy and homonymy (International Organization for Standardization, 2019; Klepousniotou et al., 2012) present a significant challenge. Several terms to do with EAMs are polysemous or homonymic, including such terms as *capability*, *concept*, *domain*, *model*, and *scope*. For such a term it may not be automatically clear which one of its definitions pertains. Furthermore, for some of these terms not even their different definitions are settled.

The observations in this section can be captured in the following problem statement:

Problem statement: No suitable applied ontology for the investigation of enterprise architecture model quality is generally available.

The problem from the problem statement above can be addressed by answering the following research question:

Research question: What constitutes a suitable applied ontology for investigating enterprise architecture model quality?

1.3 Structure of this thesis

The structure for this thesis is as follows:

- Chapter 2 “Research method” describes the research approach, the expected results, and how these results are validated.
- Chapter 3 “Backgrounds and conventions” establishes the context of enterprise architecture for which the ontology is being drafted; provides the epistemic stance for this thesis; outlines the approach to creating and validating definitions; describes the conventions for naming terms and relations; sketches how the ontology is captured in an OntoUML model; and has a section on the meaning of purpose, goal, and objective.
- Chapter 4 “A definition for EA Model” deals with expanding and specializing the definition for *conceptual model* into a definition for an enterprise architecture model, as well as an initial theory of modeling.

- Chapter 5 “The Domain Lexicon for EAMOn” then uses the concepts from chapters 3 and 4 to create a single model of twenty terms and forty-one relations, that form the desired ontology for EAM quality. The lexicon thus uncovered is an embodiment of a theory of modeling specifically for EAMs.
- Chapter 6 “Practical Application of EAMOn” covers how I draft some practical guidelines that will serve to improve model quality and reduce modeling effort, based on the theory of modeling uncovered in the prior chapter 4.
- Chapter 7 “Validity of EAMOn” addresses the validity of the uncovered ontology.
- Chapter 8 “Results and Discussion” concludes this thesis with a short summary of the results, a critical evaluation, and an overview of further work.

CHAPTER 2

Research method

2.1 Research approach

In order to address the research question from chapter 1, the task is to obtain an *applied ontology* that is suitable for the domain of [Enterprise Architecture Models \(EAMs\)](#) and EAM quality.

Ontology development is generally considered to be an engineering activity ([Kendall & McGuinness, 2019, ch.2](#)). It needs to start with establishing both a scope for the ontology, as well as criteria with which to determine when the ontology development is done. For this, Kendall and McGuinness ([2019, ch.3](#)) advocate a use case based approach, whereby a collection of use cases determine the scope and content of the ontology. Unfortunately, the discipline of [Enterprise Architecture \(EA\)](#) and the field of EA modeling are too immature to have a lexicon that is both comprehensive and generally accepted. Terms that are familiar to subject matter expert in one organization may be totally unrecognizable by subject matter experts elsewhere. Furthermore, the subject matter experts are lacking the language to discuss EA model quality altogether, as mentioned in section 1.2. Thus, surveying subject matter experts to uncover a lexicon pertaining to EA modeling is not considered a viable approach.

A second approach then, is to start the ontology development from a suitable theory for the domain. However, there is no theory of EA modeling available with sufficient amount of detail, so that it can serve as a basis to derive terms and definitions that factor in the creation and exploitation of EA models – even though there are many candidates with varying scopes and degrees of scientific underpinning, such as [Lankhorst et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Sandkuhl et al. \(2018\)](#). For the wider domain of conceptual models, there also is no a generally accepted lexicon or sufficiently detailed theory of modeling – even though here also there is no shortage of candidates, such as [Hestenes \(2010\)](#), [Mayr and Thalheim \(2020\)](#), and [Muller et al. \(2012\)](#).

The way forward, then, is to uncover the ontology by making use of, and combining, those materials that are available and suitable. A first set of such materials is the existing body of knowledge for the field of EA, as these provide the context for which the ontology must be valid. A second set of materials consists of well-researched definitions for the concept of a “model” that provide essential characteristics, as each of these characteristics gives rise to one or more concepts for the ontology. A third set of materials is the set of established theories that cover knowledge and meaning, since these can be applied to domain models such as EAMs ([Guizzardi, 2005, ch.2](#)).

To come to an applied ontology from these sets of materials, I will execute the following steps:

1. I will start from the definition of *domain model*, as has been used in research on modeling and on [Return on Modeling Effort \(RoME\)](#) ([Proper & Guizzardi, 2022](#)). Applying the analytical method of definition (appendix A) will then result in an expanded definition for “domain model”.

2. I then clarify the characteristics of the definition for “domain model” using existing theories of meaning, such as Concept Theory (Dahlberg, 1978) and the semiotic triangle (Proper & Guizzardi, 2020b).
3. The expanded definition for domain model can then be refined into a definition for EAM, with properly defined essential characteristics.
4. From this, I can arrive at properly defined concepts and relations that fully cover the domain of EA modeling and EAMs.
5. I then express these uncovered concepts and relations in OntoUML. OntoUML is an UML extension that builds upon the Unified Foundational Ontology (UFO) (Guizzardi, 2005), so as to provide an ontologically well-founded language (Guizzardi et al., 2015). A syntactically valid encoding of the ontology in OntoUML guarantees that the ontology aligns with the UFO foundational ontology (Benevides & Guizzardi, 2009; Guizzardi et al., 2022).

For both the evaluation of existing definitions and for the drafting of new definitions, I follow the methods described in appendix A.

2.2 The resulting ontology: EAMOn

The outcome of the approach from section 2.1 will be:

- A list of core concepts that are relevant in describing or researching EA modeling.
- The definition for each of these concepts, in a form that satisfies both International Organization for Standardization (2022b) and the criteria for definitions from table 3 described in appendix A.3.
- The relations between each of these concepts, with definition for some of these.
- A conceptual model (terms and relations) that covers both the activity of EA modeling and its result (the EAM).

Thus, this outcome forms an applied ontology specifically geared toward the creation, use, and research of EAMs, including their quality. This ontology will be labeled [Enterprise Architecture Model Ontology \(EAMOn\)](#).

2.3 Validating EAMOn

The validity of an ontology can be checked on two fronts: content validity, and application validity (Steiner & Albert, 2017). To validate EAMOn I perform the following actions:

- While creating the ontology, I keep in mind the contents of the Ontology Pitfall Scanner! (OOPS!) (Poveda-Villalón et al., 2014; Villalón, 2021), which is a “Catalogue of common pitfalls” for ontology work. This provides the first step in ensuring content validity (Steiner & Albert, 2017, p.5).
- I perform an ontological analysis (Azevedo et al., 2015) by performing an automated syntax check of the OntoUML representation of EAMOn. This constitutes a second step in content validity.
- For application validity (Steiner & Albert, 2017, p.6), I use EAMOn to capture the EA modeling process, and identifying quality influences it that process. From these quality influences, I can then formulate modeling guidelines that assist the EA modeler in safeguarding the quality influences. These guidelines are then compared to the advice given by an authoritative work on EA modeling that combines best practices and scientific results. This shows that the vocabulary is applicable, and covers all of the basics of EA models and EA modeling.

Any ontology is always a living document, subject to maintenance and evolution (Kendall & McGuinness, 2019). The validation phase thus is not meant to show that EAMOn is “finished”, but rather that it is of sufficient completeness and quality to be used and expanded in practice.

CHAPTER 3

Backgrounds and conventions

3.1 The interpretation of the term Enterprise Architecture

The term EA itself is understood in many different ways (Lapalme, 2012). I consider myself a member of Lapalme's second school of thought on EA, which he labeled *Enterprise Integrating*. For this school of thought, Lapalme offers the following scope and goal³ (Lapalme, 2012, p.38):

- **Scope:** “the enterprise as a sociocultural, techno-economic system, including all facets of the enterprise (where enterprise IT is just one facet)”
- **Goal:** “effectively implement the overall enterprise strategy by designing the various enterprise facets (governance structures, IT capabilities, remuneration policies, work design, and so on) to maximize coherency between them and minimize contradictions.”

Thus, when I reference the use of an [Enterprise Architecture Model \(EAM\)](#) in this thesis, I will assume that the EA model is being used within the scope given above, and is expected to contribute to the goal given above.

3.2 Epistemic stance

Doing research means implicitly or explicitly making assumptions, among which are philosophical assumptions. As the research in this thesis is foundational in nature, specifically my epistemic stance needs to be made explicitly clear (Bell et al., 2022, ch.2).

When considering models and their relation to the world, I take the stance of critical realism (Mingers et al., 2013). This entails that I believe there is an inherently intransitive domain of items, objects, events and such, independent of human observers (conform the philosophic stance of realism). By contrast, I believe our knowledge of this domain is entirely dependent on us as observers and thinkers; knowledge exists in a transitive domain that is separate from the domain to which it pertains. But while knowledge and observation is thus epistemically relative, I do not hold that views and judgments are equally relative; my stance is critical in the Kantian sense.

3.3 Conventions for naming terms and relations

I will attempt to express every term of [EAMOn](#) as a noun. Furthermore, every relation between these terms will be expressed as a verb, for which I will provide the present simple form, except for their formal

³Lapalme actually uses the term *purpose*, but I will introduce in section 3.5 specific meanings for both the words “purpose” and “goal”, so that I have to replace *purpose* with *goal* here.

definition, which will present the gerund form as the definiendum. I distinguish between relations and relationships, whereby the concept of relationship is the truthmaker for the relation⁴. Every relationship that describes a relation will be labeled with the noun that corresponds with the verb of that relation.

To make the lexicon maximally clear and avoid ambiguity (where feasible), I will avoid using polysemic or homonymic words and verbs (as mentioned in chapter 1). This includes avoiding the use of the same noun or verb for more than one term, relation, or relationship, as that effectively introduces polysemy. I also strive to avoid words and verbs that are so generic and common as to not readily be recognizable as a specific term, such as *has* and *is*. Exceptions to the conventions provided above are the following special cases:

- *Has* will be used for all relations between some term that refers to something that has attributes and/or properties, and those attributes or properties. This is because I feel it would be very contrived to say something other than that something *has* that attribute or property. Furthermore, *has* is a fitting word that describes the relation between a composing or aggregating concept, and the other concept(s) that it is composing or aggregating.
- *Aggregates* will be used for every aggregation, *composes* will be used for every composition.
- *Conceives* will be used as the relation in every case where an actor creates in their mind some concept, even if these concepts are (vastly) different.
- Likewise, *consults* will be used as the relation in every case where an actor thinks of some concept, cognitively manipulates that concept present in their mind, or extracts information from their mental model of that concept.

For every concept (term) that I am going to describe, I will use a capital letter at the beginning of the first word that signifies the concept. Thus, when I write something like Architecture concept, I am formally referencing a specific concept that must have been introduced earlier (or is just being introduced for the first time). I have opted not do this for the relations, as capitalized verbs make for very stilted reading. Furthermore, when informally referencing a concept, as well as when using the formal concept in a definiens, I will forego this capitalization convention.

3.4 Presenting EAMOn in OntoUML

Guizzardi (2005) proposes a variant of UML specifically to express ontologies, based on the concepts contained in the [Unified Foundational Ontology \(UFO\)](#). This language is ontologically well-founded, meaning that its modeling primitives are derived from a proper foundational ontology – UFO itself. This modeling language has since been labeled OntoUML.

[EAMOn](#) will be captured in an OntoUML model, which in turn will be presented in this thesis in a number of separate views. In these views, each concept will be captured as an OntoUML class, such as $\langle\langle\text{kind}\rangle\rangle$, $\langle\langle\text{role}\rangle\rangle$, $\langle\langle\text{collective}\rangle\rangle$, and $\langle\langle\text{quality}\rangle\rangle$. The relations between these will in most cases be $\langle\langle\text{material}\rangle\rangle$ relations. Each of these will be associated with a $\langle\langle\text{relator}\rangle\rangle$ concept that encodes the relationship ([Guarino & Guizzardi, 2015](#)), which itself is connected to the two concepts at the end points of the relation via two $\langle\langle\text{mediation}\rangle\rangle$ relations. Further relation types that will be required are $\langle\langle\text{componentOf}\rangle\rangle$ relations (for *aggregates* and *composes* relations), $\langle\langle\text{specialization}\rangle\rangle$ relations, and $\langle\langle\text{characterization}\rangle\rangle$ relations.

The different OntoUML views will also present the multiplicity of each relation, as defined in UML ([Seidl et al., 2015](#)). Multiplicity indicates how many instances of one class can be considered connected to an instance of another class through a given relation, and vice versa. This relation is presented as a string that indicates the lower and upper bounds at the endpoints of the relation. A detailed analysis of the meaning and implication of each of the provided multiplicities is beyond the scope of this thesis, and will be presented in future work.

⁴An explanation of the difference between relation and relationship can be found in Guarino and Guizzardi (2015).

3.5 Purpose, goal, and objective

Part of the discussion of models is the term *purpose*. It is customary to speak of an item's purpose, and models are no exception. But in everyday speech, this word purpose is not used consistently; it is often used interchangeably with goal and objective. As an illustration, consider some dictionary definitions for "purpose" ("Purpose", n.d.; "Purpose", n.d.), "goal" ("Goal", n.d.; "Goal", n.d.), and "objective" ("Objective", n.d.; "Objective", n.d.). These show how the colloquial meaning of the three words spill into each other, making each (almost, although not quite) a synonym for the others.

To avoid any confusion when using any of these words, it is necessary to assign to each some unambiguous, non-synonymous meaning. I will explicitly posit and use definitions to that end, since the references provided above show that dictionaries by themselves cannot provide the required clarity. Based on the dictionary entries given above, the definitions I will use throughout this thesis are:

Definition 3.1 Purpose: *the motive or reason that an actor has, that explains why it is or should be the case that a goal is desired, an object exists, or an action is carried out,*

Definition 3.2 Goal: *a (usually lofty, qualitative, and long-term) end state that an actor strives for, towards which effort is directed.*

Definition 3.3 Objective: *a (usually specific, concrete, and near-term) result that an actor pursues, as they expect it to contribute to one or more of their goals.*

These definitions all involve an actor. For a definition of actor, I make use of a common definition from the professional literature:

Definition 3.4 Actor: *A person, organization, or system that has one or more roles that initiates or interacts with activities. (The Open Group, 2022d, p. 4.2)*

I need to stress that that purpose, goal, and objective all exist in the human mind, be it a single person or a collection thereof. Thus, if the actor in definition 3.1, 3.2, or 3.3 is actually a system, then the purpose, goal, or objective necessarily resides in one or more humans that *employ* that specific system, rather than the system itself.

The causal link to the rest of the world is played by the *result* mentioned in definition 3.3. Within the context of purpose, goal, and objective, I now define the term result as:

Definition 3.5 Result: *an outcome or situation that exists at the conclusion of some action.*

If a given actor pursues a certain objective, it is likely that they will also pursue some result that achieves this objective. Nevertheless, definition 3.5 is not explicitly tied to any actor. This is because it could be the case that a result is obtained indirectly, or by some uninvolved actor, or even by random chance.

Definitions 3.1 through 3.5 validate well against the criteria for definitions from appendix A.3, and allow for unambiguously identifying and labeling different useful concepts and their interrelations. On these definitions, an actor can have some purpose (a motive), to which they then formulate and pursue a goal (the end state they wish to achieve) which will fulfill their purpose. They can then strive towards that goal by pursuing one or more objectives that each contribute to that goal. That objective can in turn be achieved in the form of a result, which is itself thus considered a contribution toward the goal. A diagram showing these terms and relations is given in fig. 1.

Figure 1: The relations between actor, purpose, goal, objective, and result.

Note: other authors are likely to use these terms and relations in a way that has a differing meaning. Therefore, if any of these terms appear in some source to be used, then it requires analysis, and sometimes remapping according to the definitions in this section, before the content of that source can be processed within the context of this thesis.

CHAPTER 4

A definition for EA Model

The concept of an [Enterprise Architecture Model \(EAM\)](#) forms the basis for [Enterprise Architecture Model Ontology \(EAMOn\)](#). All other terms in the applied ontology are dependent on it, directly or indirectly. In this chapter I will arrive at an analytical definition for the concept of an EAM, including the definitions of its essential characteristics.

4.1 A hierarchy of model categories?

The analytical method described in [appendix A](#) provides a means to arrive at a definition of some term, by departing from a definition for the immediate superordinate concept. This then raises the question: in a hierarchy of model categories, which model category forms the immediate superordinate concept?

Unfortunately, few general taxonomies have been proposed for models, and those that have been, such as [Highland \(1973\)](#) and [Mendel \(2012\)](#), do not include EA models, nor are they readily extendable to do so. It seems that the theoretical knowledge in the area of modeling is insufficient to draw up a valid taxonomy. Or it may be the case that the nature of models and their use is such that a model created for a real-world application can have characteristics placing it on or between multiple taxa. The fact that terms are defined and used differently and with different (often implicit) assumptions between disciplines, and even between individual authors within a discipline, complicates matters further.

In any case, a hierarchy of model categories containing [EAMs](#) currently does not readily present itself. The next best option then is to obtain an analytical definition of a concept that can safely be considered superordinate to EAM, without regard of it being *immediately* superordinate.

I will now make the assumption that for the term EAM, the concept of a “domain model” presents a suitable superordinate concept. Because of this assumption, the characteristics of this concept will carry over into the definition of an EAM, while the specific circumstances and uses of it will introduce new or specialized characteristics.

4.2 The definition of “Domain model”

To analyze the attributes of the concept of a Domain model I will start from the following definition:

Definition 4.1 Domain model: *A social artifact that is understood, and acknowledged, by a collective human agent to represent an abstraction of some domain for a particular cognitive purpose. ([Proper & Guizzardi, 2022](#))*

This definition is based on foundational work by e.g. Apostel (1961) and Stachowiak (1973), more recent work on the same by different authors (Harel & Rumpe, 2004; Rothenberg, 1989; Sandkuhl et al., 2018; Thalheim, 2011), as well as recent research into modeling and Return on Modeling Effort (RoME) (Bjeković et al., 2014; Guarino et al., 2019; Guizzardi, 2006; Hoppenbrouwers et al., 2005; Proper & Guizzardi, 2020a; 2020b; Proper et al., 2005). Thus it is sufficiently well-founded.

A description of the essential attributes of definition 4.1 is provided in Proper and Guizzardi (2022) as follows:

- *Social artifact*: A model is seen as a social artifact in the sense that its role as a model should be recognizable by a collective agent (e.g. people).
- *Collective Agent*: The collective agent observes the domain by way of their senses and/or by way of (collective) self-reflection, and, based on this, should acknowledge/accept the artifact as indeed being a model of the domain (for a given purpose).
- *Abstraction*: a model is the representation of an abstraction. This implies that, in line with the cognitive purpose of the model, some (if not most) details of the domain are consciously filtered out.
- *Domain*: domain refers to *anything* that one can speak and/or reflect about; i.e. the domain of interest. As such, domain simply refers to *that what is being modeled*.
- *Cognitive purpose*: A model must always be created for some cognitive purpose; i.e. to express, specify, learn about, or experience, knowledge regarding the modeled domain. As a direct corollary to this, one can conclude that a model, being a social artifact, must be a language utterance. Thus: a model is a social-linguistic artifact.

Definition 4.1 satisfies the criteria for definitions in table 3 from section A.2, however the essential attributes are defined somewhat terse. Clarifying and elaborating these essential attributes will serve to improve and expand definition 4.1. This will be the goal of the next section.

4.3 Augmented definitions for the essential attributes of a “Domain model”

A Domain model serves a goal, and therefore has an audience

In definition 4.1 the essential attribute of *cognitive purpose* is being employed. However, I have argued in section 3.5 that purpose (like goal and objective) is held by an actor (section 3.5); therefore it cannot be that the domain model itself intrinsically *has* that purpose. I now stipulate that *cognitive purpose* in definition 4.1 must be considered a shorthand form of: the Domain model is a result that is intended to contribute to a (specifically cognitive) Goal, held by some Actor or Actors. But it is not sufficient to refer to these as the collective agent in definition 4.1, as the goals of the actors *using* the domain model may not fully align with those of the actors *creating* the domain model.

Making use of the definitions from section 3.5, I will now introduce a distinction between those who *create* domain models, and those that *make use of them*. To this end, I label the actor that creates a model the *Modeler*. The collection of the actor or actors that make use of the domain model I label the *Model audience*, with the individual actors being *Model audience members*. Thus a Model audience is a collection of one or more Model audience members, whose Goals the Domain model is directly intended to contribute to. Note that a domain model may be created and used to contribute to goals of actors that are expected to directly interact with the domain model, as well as actors that will never interact with it. I will not take this second group into consideration in this thesis.

For an actor to be motivated to actually use the domain model, they must believe that using it will result in some contribution to their goals (which was signaled in definition 4.1 by employing the term *acknowledge*). To be able to distinguish between those that directly interact with domain models and those that benefit indirectly, I now introduce the following definition:

Definition 4.2 Consuming: *the action, performed by an actor, of directly interacting with a domain model, independent of other actors or their assistance, on the belief that this contributes to some cognitive goal of that actor.*

Thus, a member of a Model audience is an Actor who is expected by the Modeler to *consume* the Domain model.

Given this line of reasoning, and given the definitions of actor and goal as provided in definitions 3.2 and 3.4, I now arrive at the following definitions:

Definition 4.3 Model audience member: *an actor who is expected to consume a domain model, on the belief that this contributes to some cognitive goal of theirs.*

Definition 4.4 Model audience member goal: *a cognitive goal, pursued by a model audience member.*

Definition 4.5 Model audience: *the aggregated set of model audience members that a domain model is intended to serve.*

Definition 4.6 Model audience goal set: *the aggregated set of the model audience member goals that a domain model is intended to contribute to.*

A graphical representation of these terms and relations is given in fig. 2.

Figure 2: The audience for a given domain model and their respective goals.

Note that it is unlikely that the different model audience members each have the same goal for which they wish to employ the domain model. Model audience member goals may be overlapping, disjunct, contradictory, or any combination thereof. The modeler therefore is not guaranteed to have a clear goal to work towards when creating the model. Instead, it is their task to size up the expected Model audience members, and formulate some *Model objective* that, if achieved, can be expected to contribute to the Model audience goal set. Once such a Model objective is formulated, the modeler can pursue this objective, with the actual Domain model the concrete Result that (wholly or partly) achieves the Model objective. This notion is graphically presented in fig. 3.

Figure 3: To contribute to the Model audience goal set, the Modeler pursues a Model objective.

Given the above, and starting from definition 3.3, I can now define the Actor that is the Modeler, and refine the “cognitive purpose” from definition 4.1 for the modeler.

This leads to the following definitions:

Definition 4.7 Modeler: *an actor that is involved in the creation, maintenance, or expansion of a model.*

Definition 4.8 Model objective: *a (usually specific, concrete, and near-term) result that a modeler pursues, as they expect it to contribute to their model audience’s goal set.*

A Domain model has a referent, and therefore captures a concept

I now turn to the essential attribute *domain* from definition 4.1. This term is polysemous, but in this context it is clear that it describes *what* it is that a domain model is referring to: it is the *referent* of the domain model. Since philosophy of language applies to domain models (Guizzardi, 2005, ch.2), I am justified to employ concept theory (Dahlberg, 1978) to clarify what role the referent plays in modeling. Concept theory offers a mapping between the referent as an *item* that is positioned in some *universe of items*, the *concept* as a “unit of knowledge”, and a *term* as the label that is used to denote that concept in some *universe of discourse*. The central idea for concept construction from Dahlberg (1978) has been reproduced⁵ in fig. 4.

Figure 4: Concept construction. Reproduced from Dahlberg (1978, fig 1).

⁵Note that Dahlberg (1978) does not follow the modeling convention that I described in section 3.4, and thus neither does fig. 4.

Concept theory generally connects the item of reference, the referent, to the word we use to refer to it, as well as the ideas we have about it. This connection is labeled in Dahlberg (1978) as the concept triangle, and is graphically presented in fig. 5.

Figure 5: Concept triangle. Reproduced from Dahlberg (1978, fig 3).

Under concept theory, the referent is an item⁶ within a universe of items, which comprises everything from ideas and objects to actions and dimensions. This Referent can then be understood by a human mind as a *Concept*, and denoted using a label, name, or *Term*. Having a term with which to communicate the concept makes it possible to employ the concept in an (inherently transitive (Mingers et al., 2013)) *Universe of discourse* (Recanati, 1996). Under concept theory⁷ a concept is itself made up of both a number of *Characteristics* and some *Term* that denotes that referent, and can be used to communicate the concept as a whole. These properties are represented in fig. 6 below.

Figure 6: Relations between referent and concept.

With this summary of concept theory in place, I can now investigate its application to domain models. I start by noting that a Domain model attempts to represent a Referent (which is referred to as the “domain” in definition 4.1). That Referent is then situated in some specific *Universe of items* (concept theory, fig. 4), which can be the intransitive reality, but also some future, contingent, or otherwise imaginable state of affairs. This implies that a Domain model must itself pertain to that specific Universe of items, and no other. This Universe of items provides the *context* for the Referent.

The domain model, and all it entails, can be assumed to be valid when discussed in a context that aligns with the specific universe of items, but cannot be assumed to be valid when discussed in another context. To be able to refer to this context, I could employ the term *possible world* from philosophy (Menzel, 2022), but this term is usually not readily understood outside of philosophy. For the activity of modeling, I therefore propose the term *Referent universe* as denoting the specific universe of items that the domain model is pertaining to.

⁶Note, however, that the item, the referent, need not be singular. It often (arguably always) concerns some constellation or aggregation of sub-items, on an arbitrary number of sub-levels. The “domain” from definition 4.1 then forms the outer wrapper of such a constellation or aggregation.

⁷Concept theory is not the only theory offering such an account; see for instance Hestenes (2010), or consider the semiotic triangle (Proper & Guizzardi, 2020a).

To be clear: the “real world” that is recognized by positivists, realists, empiricists, and the like, is a universe of items. Any past or future state of the real world is also a universe of items, distinct from the real world because of its position in time. But the mental image of reality that we have in our heads is *not* a universe of items, but rather a set of concepts that reference it.

I can now craft the following definitions:

Definition 4.9 Referent: *an item positioned in a referent universe.*

Definition 4.10 Referent universe: *some universe of items, in which the item that is of interest to the modeler exists.*

In both of these definitions, an *item* can be anything: “... a single object, a set of objects considered as a unit, or a property, an action, a dimension, etc. or any combination of these.” (Dahlberg, 1978, p.143).

Next, I note that a domain model is expected to contribute to the cognitive goals of a set of model audience members (definitions 4.3 through 4.6). In terms of concept theory, this means that the domain model is communicating units of knowledge, i.e. concepts. As philosophy of language applies to domain models, I can say that a domain model serves in a discourse between modeler and audience (even though this discourse will resemble a monologue). This means that the scope that a Domain model covers (or intends to cover, or is expected to cover) maps to the *Universe of discourse* from concept theory. In the context of modeling, I label a domain model’s transient universe of discourse the *Model universe*⁸. Thus I arrive at these two definitions:

Definition 4.11 Concept: *a knowledge unit comprising the characteristics of a referent, a term or a name (Dahlberg, 1978, p.144), and a meaning.*

Definition 4.12 Model Universe: *the universe of discourse within which the model is situated.*

I want to stress the importance of properly distinguishing between the *Referent universe* and the *Model universe*. The former denotes the circumstances and context of the referent that the domain model is trying to reference - some actual (or potentially actual) state of affairs. The latter provides the Universe of discourse, containing the context and background for the Domain model itself - some understanding of the referent universe by an actor that they uses in their inner dialogue, or shared by a group of actors in explicit communication.

To find the relations between the Model, Referent, and their respective Universes, as well as their relation with concepts, I can make use of the semiotic triangle by Ogden and Richards, similar to the way shown in Proper and Guizzardi (2020a). Where the semiotic triangle has at its corners: *symbol*, *thought or reference*, and *referent*, I now position the model, the concept, and the referent, respectively. Connecting these with the three relations from the semiotic triangle (symbolizes, references, and stands for), I arrive at fig. 7 depicted below. Additionally, I posit that the Referent universe *informs* the Model universe.

⁸This is not a new insight. In Nelson et al. (2011, ch.3), the Model universe is recognized, although labeled there as the “physical domain”.

Figure 7: Model, Referent and Concept in the semiotic triangle.

A Domain model is a social artefact

Definition 4.1 declares a domain model to be a specific kind of social artifact, stemming from the observation that domain models are created by humans, and then used in a social setting. Given its position in definition 4.1, the concept of “social artifact” is a superordinate concept for “domain model”. Therefore a more explicit definition than the terse description from Proper and Guizzardi (2022) is in order. Based on dictionary definitions such as “Artifact” (n.d.) I state:

Definition 4.13 Social artifact: *something produced by humans, to be employed in a social setting.*

A Domain model is cost-effective, and therefore has associated value and cost

I am interested in the costs and benefits that domain models bring to their users. These costs and benefits can be evaluated using the concept of RoME (Proper & Guizzardi, 2022). But neither the costs nor the benefits of creating and using domain models are reflected in definition 4.1. By contrast, some of the extant definitions for models in general do take costs and benefits into account, to a certain extent.

Rothenberg recognized that any model is characterized, among other aspects, by it being *cost-effective*, stating that “It is more cost-effective to use the model [...] than to use the referent itself” (Rothenberg, 1989). Given this, I argue that cost-effectiveness must be considered an essential characteristic of a domain model, and thus must be added to its definition.

Adding cost-effectiveness to definition 4.1 requires also obtaining a definition for this characteristic itself, per the reasoning in section A.2. But for this, Rothenberg offers little assistance: cost-effectiveness is simply considered the difference between the cost of manipulating the model and the cost of manipulating the referent directly. But this approach does not consider the possibility of new or extra value arising from the *creation* of the model itself, nor are the costs taken into account that are associated with the creation and maintenance of the model.

A slightly more elaborate appraisal of the value of models is provided by Nickerson and Boyd (1980), which considers the use of models in the domain of decision analysis. On this approach, some actor can either take action without making use of models, or they can have a model created, and then take action supported by the information provided by the model. In Nickerson and Boyd (1980), the difference in the value of the actions taken without and with the model is considered the value that modeling brings, expressed as the *Expected Value of Modeling (EVM)*. This approach focuses on value rather than cost; it does not take into consideration the costs that are associated with the creation and use of the model.

Mindful of the contributions by both Rothenberg and by Nickerson and Boyd, I introduce the following expression for cost-effectiveness:

Definition 4.14 *Model cost-effectiveness*: *the ratio between the sum total value that the model audience can extract from the model, and the sum total value of the effort of constructing and maintaining the model and of consuming the model.*

In this definition, the two essential attributes are:

- **The sum total value that the model audience can extract from using the model:** this is the sum of the value that befalls each of the model audience’s members when they are using the model, minus the value that would befall them if they did not use the model (say, if they used the referent directly, or did nothing at all);
- **The sum total value of the effort of constructing and maintaining the model and of consuming the model:** constructing and maintaining the model will have associated cost; consuming the model may also have associated cost, such as the time spent on consuming it. The sum of these costs will have a non-zero value.

Both the value that the model audience obtains, and the cost that the modeler and model audience expend, need to be in the same currency; for example money, time, transactions, or person-hours. Furthermore, you cannot choose a currency for which the cost of creating and consuming the model is zero. If both these conditions are satisfied, then the cost-effectiveness ratio is a dimensionless number. If this number is higher than one, then the use of the model is cost-effective for the chosen currency: it provides more value (in the chosen currency) than the costs that it incurs (in that same currency).

4.4 An expanded definition for “Domain model”

Given the considerations and definitions from section 4.3, I hereby propose the following definition for *Domain model* as an expanded form of definition 4.1:

Definition 4.15 *Domain model*: *a social artefact reflecting a concept, intended to cost-effectively pursue a particular cognitive objective in support of a particular audience.*

The definitions for the essential characteristics in this definition are given here:

- Social artifact: definition 4.13;
- Concept: definition 4.11;
- (Model) cost-effectiveness: definition 4.14;
- (Model) objective: definition 4.8;
- (Model) audience: definition 4.5.

4.5 A definition for “Enterprise architecture model”

Note: every term and relation in the remainder of this thesis refers specifically to the use of modeling within the context of [Enterprise Architecture \(EA\)](#). But in creating the labels I will consistently abbreviate the prefixes “enterprise architecture” to EA, and “enterprise architecture model” to EAM, to shorten the labels and improve readability - except in definitions. Thus I write *EA modeler* instead of *enterprise architecture modeler*, *EAM* instead of *enterprise architecture model*, *EAM audience member* instead of *enterprise architecture model audience member*, et cetera.

As stated in chapter 1, my interest is in [EAMs](#) and their quality. And as stated at the beginning of this chapter: a definition for EAM can be arrived at by departing from the definition of its superordinate concept, followed by the delimiting characteristics (conform [appendix A](#)). I thus start from [definition 4.15](#), and take into consideration the following points.

The *audience* of an EAM will consist of actors that have an interest in some change within the enterprise. These actors are considered *stakeholders* for the change under consideration. However, not every stakeholder will have the required competencies to fully make use of a given EAM; for instance they may not be able to read the used EA modeling language. Such a person will then still be a stakeholder, but cannot be a member of the EAM audience. (Conversely, if this person must be a member of the EAM audience, then the modeler cannot use that particular EA modeling language for the EAM.) Given these restrictions, I come to the following [definition 4.16](#) for an EAM audience member.

Definition 4.16 *Enterprise architecture model audience member*: *an actor who is expected to independently interact with a specific enterprise architecture model, on the belief that this interaction will contribute to some cognitive goal of theirs.*

In this definition, *independently* means “without assistance from any other person”, and this includes the EA modeler.

The *EAM audience* as a whole consists of one or more EAM audience members, which leads to the following [definition 4.17](#):

Definition 4.17 *Enterprise architecture model audience*: *a set of enterprise architecture model audience members that are each expected to independently interact with a specific enterprise architecture model.*

The *cognitive objective* that the EAM intends to pursue is focused on the information needs that the members of this EAM audience have.

The *concept* that the EAM reflects will be the *architecture* under consideration. This term has many definitions, but I will not spend time on it in this thesis. Instead I will here adopt the definition from *ISO/IEC/IEEE 42010:2022(E)*, as this is considered an authoritative source in the profession of EA (for instance being referenced by the [The Open Group Architecture Framework \(TOGAF\)](#) standard):

Definition 4.18 *Enterprise architecture*: *fundamental concepts or properties of an entity in its environment and governing principles for the realization and evolution of this entity and its related life cycle processes. (*International Organization for Standardization, 2022a, p. 3.2*)*

Applying the above to [definition 4.15](#), I arrive at the following [definition 4.19](#) for an EAM:

Definition 4.19 *Enterprise architecture model*: *a social artefact reflecting an enterprise architecture, intended to cost-effectively pursue a particular cognitive objective in support of a particular audience.*

The definitions for the essential characteristics in this definition are given here:

- Social artifact: [definition 4.13](#);
- Enterprise architecture: [definition 4.18](#);
- Cost-effectiveness: [definition 4.14](#);
- Objective: [definition 3.3](#);
- Audience (here meaning Enterprise architecture model audience): [definition 4.17](#).

CHAPTER 5

The domain lexicon for EAMOn

In this chapter I will make use of the definitions obtained in chapter 4, to now construct an ontology for the domain of [Enterprise Architecture \(EA\)](#) modeling. This ontology consists of:

- A domain lexicon: all the terms and their definitions for the domain of EA modeling,
- The relations between these concepts,
- And a graphical representation of these terms and relations in OntoUML.

The primary means by which I arrive at the ontology is by methodically compiling the domain lexicon from the definitions in the last chapter, taking into consideration the context of EA from section 3.1.

5.1 Positioning the architecture

I begin by considering the position of the [Enterprise Architecture Model \(EAM\)](#), the information about the change of the enterprise that it intends to capture, and the contexts of both of these. For this, we look at chapter 4, specifically the concepts of Referent, Referent universe, Model, and Model universe, as captured in fig. 7. These concepts then lead to EA-specific versions, to begin with the referent and its context.

In EA, the referent of a model equates to the part of the enterprise that is under consideration for some form of change. This referent may be anything, from a value chain down to a sub-process, from an entire ICT infrastructure landscape to a single system, from an information landscape to a single data set, and more. For the concept of referent I select the label “System”, as I deem the label “referent” itself too theoretical for EA modelers in practice. Consequentially the Universe of items in which such a System is positioned can best be labeled the “System universe”. Adapting definitions 4.9 and 4.10, I arrive at the following, EA specific, definitions:

Definition 5.1 System: *An item of interest within the enterprise that is the subject of an enterprise architecture model, whereby “item” can be anything from ideas and objects to processes and information, or aggregations thereof.*

Definition 5.2 System universe: *the universe of items that harbors the system that is the subject of the enterprise architecture model; the context in which that system exists.*

The EAM that has the system as its subject has itself been defined in definition 4.19. But as the previous section, and specifically fig. 7 indicate: an EAM exists within a specific universe that contains and provides the context for that EAM. This is captured in the following definition 5.3:

Definition 5.3 Enterprise architecture model universe: *the universe of discourse that covers the part of the enterprise and its surroundings that fully envelopes the system that is the subject of the enterprise architecture model, including all parts of the enterprise that themselves change if the system is changed.*

The four terms above are related by four relations. Two of these are straightforward: an EAM is part of an EAM universe, and a System is part of a System universe. The third relation is the one between EAM and the System that it references; from the semiotic triangle and fig. 7 I can infer that an EAM *stands for* the System that is being modeled. The fourth relation is between the two universes: in line with what I posited in section 4.3, I say that the System universe *informs* the EAM universe, in that the information captured in that EAM universe must originate from, and correspond with, the System universe.

The representation in OntoUML of these four terms and their interrelations is provided below in fig. 8. Note that the two material relations are associated with a `<<relator>>` concept, which disambiguates the relation, providing the material conditions that act as truthmakers for the relation (Guarino & Guizzardi, 2015). I label the relators and include them in the OntoUML diagrams, but I will not further document them in this thesis, instead relegating that work to future publications.

Figure 8: Positioning the EA model.

5.2 Conceiving the architecture

I now turn to the question how the EA that is to be captured in the EAM gets *conceived*. This conception is carried out by the *EA modeler*, a role assigned to an Actor, that entails working on and with EAMs. Starting out from definition 4.7, I come to the following definition:

Definition 5.4 Enterprise architecture modeler: *a role, assigned to an actor, requiring the creation, maintenance, or expansion of an enterprise architecture model.*

In the first phase of modeling, the EA modeler will need to create in their mind a conception of the system that is under consideration, existing in some system universe – as defined in section 5.1. In order to be able to consider the system itself, the modeler inevitably will also have to consider the context of the system, and thus the relevant sections of the system universe; this means the modeler needs to *conceive* both the system itself, and at a minimum that part of the system universe with which the system interacts, or which has a (direct or indirect) influence on the system.

Note that in some cases, this System universe may actually coincide with current reality (the *World*); this pertains in particular when the EA modeler is creating a baseline architecture, documenting what is already there. In that case, certain elements⁹ of that system can likely be conceived by directly *perceiving* the world. A definition for that concept, aligning with my epistemic stance as described in section 3.2 is the following:

Definition 5.5 *World*: *the state of things as they are, outside and independent of any observer.*

Once the concept of the system manifests itself in the mind of the EA modeler, they can then work with that concept, in order to investigate the enterprise architecture of that system. This will lead to the forming in their mind of another concept, namely the *Architecture concept*. This concept comprises the knowledge about the architecture of the System that the EA modeler will (attempt to) capture in the EAM.

Definition 5.6 *Architecture concept*: *a knowledge unit (characteristics, meaning, and a term or label) that comprises the enterprise architecture of a system.*

The representation in OntoUML of the terms and relations as presented above is depicted below in fig. 9.

⁹Note, however, that some elements of the system are not directly perceivable even in the real world. As an example, consider some law or regulation that exist in the real world. EA modelers will not be able to perceive this law or regulation itself. Instead they can only read the text that records that law or regulation, and conceive of it in their mind.

Figure 9: How the modeler conceives an enterprise architecture.

5.3 Modeling the architecture

Following the conception of the architecture, the EA modeler is able to consult the Architecture concept that they conceived in their mind. From that, they can then construct the actual *EAM* (defined in definition 4.19).

I now turn to the *EAM* itself, as a thing that the EA modeler is constructing. It must have some sort of perceptible form (for example a drawing on paper, or an electronic image), or it could not be read by its intended audience. Furthermore, it must have an information content, or it could not serve the cognitive goals of its intended audience. The distinction between form and content is discussed in Mahr (2011), which states that in a model, object M carries cargo χ , and that this object M corresponds to model μ (explicitly using the word “is” for that correspondence relation). I will incorporate the distinction that Mahr makes. However, the usage of labels like M , μ , and χ are not native to EA practitioners, and I already use *EAM* instead of Mahr’s μ . I thus propose to introduce the following terms to refer to object M and cargo χ :

- an *EAM* has an *EAM content*, the information that reflects the architecture that the EA modeler attempts to capture. This corresponds with Mahr’s concept χ .
- The *EAM content* is carried by some form of *EAM embodiment*. This corresponds to Mahr’s concept M .

Interpreting the description of M and χ from Mahr (2011), I create the following definitions:

Definition 5.7 Enterprise architecture model content: *the information that reflects the enterprise architecture that an enterprise architecture modeler attempts to capture.*

Definition 5.8 Enterprise architecture model embodiment: *the perceptible form of an enterprise architecture model that carries the enterprise architecture model content, and in doing so expresses the architecture concept.*

The terms above are connected by the following material relations:

- Between EA modeler and Architecture concept: the EA modeler holds in his mind the architecture as a concept, a unit of knowledge. When creating the *EAM*, he will be *consulting* this knowledge.
- Between EA modeler and *EAM*: this relation covers the fact that *EAMs* are created by EA modelers; a common term for that is *constructing*¹⁰.
- Between the EA modeler and the *EAM embodiment*: the actual activity that produces the embodiment is dubbed *writing*, reflecting the fact that an *EAM* usually is embodied in diagrams and texts.
- The relation between *EAM embodiment* and *EAM content* is dubbed by Mahr (2011) to be *carrying*. I will employ the same label.

There are two more relations, which are not material. According to Mahr (2011) a model embodiment *is* a model, or conversely that a model *has* a model embodiment. But as I wish to avoid the verb *is*, I elect to use *composes*. Thus, an *EAM* is:

- *composed of* an *EAM embodiment*, and
- *composed of* *EAM content*.

Note that direct relations are provided between the EA modeler and the *EAM* as a whole, and between the EA modeler and the *EAM embodiment*. By contrast, I provide no direct relation between the EA modeler and the *EAM content*. This is because the *EAM content* is carried by the *EAM embodiment*, and is not directly accessible by the EA modeler, other than by manipulating that *EAM embodiment*.

I provide the OntoUML representation of the terms and relations below in fig. 10.

¹⁰Note that the term *modeling* is less suitable, since that is usually understood to include the ideation and conceptualization of the architecture, not “just” the creation of the artefact that will be the *EAM*.

Figure 10: The terms surrounding the modeling of the EA.

5.4 Consuming the Enterprise architecture model

There is at least one *EAM audience member*, someone who is potentially or actually going to consume the EAM – see definitions 4.2 and 4.16. Such an EAM audience member, after consuming the EAM, will have in their mind as a concept some part of the architecture that the EA modeler used to construct the model. However, the concept conceived by the EAM audience member likely is not exactly the same as the concept that the EA modeler conceived, as communication is inherently lossy, and an EAM audience member will rarely have exactly the background knowledge quite like the EA modeler anticipated. Furthermore, the EAM audience member may have a limited interest in the architecture, and thus not feel the need to consume the EAM in its entirety, instead only consuming some part that is relevant to them. Because of this, such an EAM audience member will then afterward have in their mind a concept that only coincides with some part of the architecture. As a result, the concept in the mind of a single EAM audience member probably diverges from the architecture in the mind of the EA modeler, both in scope and accuracy. It is therefore a different concept, and consequentially gets its own label, namely *Architecture concept**. Derived from definition 5.6, this concept gets the following definition:

Definition 5.9 *Architecture concept:** *a knowledge unit that comprises the enterprise architecture of a system, or part thereof, as it is learned by a stakeholder from an enterprise architecture model.*

When an EAM audience member consumes an EAM, there are three relations in play:

- Between the EAM audience member and the EAM: this relation is named *consuming* (definition 4.2), and considered an independent interaction with the EAM.
- Between the EAM audience member and the EAM embodiment: this relation is dubbed *reading*, mirroring the writing relation posited in section 5.3.
- Between the EAM audience member and the *Architecture concept**: by consuming the EAM, the EAM audience member will learn about (some of) the content of the EAM, constructing some men-

I have provided the representation in OntoUML of these specialized terms and relations below in fig. 12.

Figure 12: OntoUML representation of the audience for a given EAM.

5.6 The relations between EAM, Architecture concept, and Architecture concept*

The Architecture concept* arrived at by an EAM audience member will correspond to a greater or lesser extent to the Architecture concept as conceived by the EA modeler. In an ideal situation (perfect EA modeler, EAM, and EAM audience member) the Architecture concept* will correspond fully to the original Architecture concept from which the EAM was created. But if the quality of the EAM is less than perfect, or if other factors intervene in the path from EA modeler’s mind to EAM audience member’s mind, then the correspondence will be less than complete. Thus, the correspondence relation plays a major role in EAM quality, such that I feel it is necessary to provide a formal definition:

Definition 5.12 Correspondence: *the degree to which the interpretation of an enterprise architecture model by an enterprise architecture audience member agrees with the architecture concept as conceived by the enterprise architecture modeler.*

Since one can understand the EAM in three different ways (as an EAM embodiment, as EAM content, and as the whole of the EAM), there are three ways to relate the EAM to the architecture:

- *Captures*: prior to this section, I have already employed the term *capturing* for the relation between Architecture concept and EAM.
- *Reflects*: note that the EAM content is the information as carried by the EAM’s embodiment, it is not the Architecture concept itself. A word that nicely expresses this epistemological ambivalence is *reflecting*. The better the EAM content is reflecting the Architecture concept, the better the EAM is from an information perspective.
- *Expresses*: I used the relation *writing* between EA modeler and EAM embodiment. Since writing is a form of expression, for the reverse relation I state that the EAM embodiment *expresses* the Architecture concept.

When an EAM audience member is consuming an EAM and conceiving the Architecture concept*, they are doing the reverse that the EA modeler was doing. It is therefore convenient to have the terms for

the relations between Architecture concept* and EAM/EAM content/EAM embodiment mirror the terms used between those and the Architecture concept:

- *Interprets*: the opposite side of expressing;
- *Matches*: this term is selected to bridge the epistemic uncertainty between Architecture concept* (a mental construct) and EAM content (information carried by the embodiment).
- *Is understanding*: When an EAM audience member is consuming the EAM, they are attempting to understand it. As a result of this activity, the Architecture concept* is the understanding that the EAM audience member gets from the EAM.

The OntoUML representation of these seven material relations is provided in fig. 13.

Figure 13: OntoUML representation of how the Architecture concept* corresponds with the Architecture concept.

5.7 How the EAM satisfies the EAM audience

The preceding texts have already addressed how the EA modeler is constructing the EAM so that the members of an EAM audience can consume it. What has not been covered is what the EA modeler needs to do to actually satisfy the needs that that EAM audience has, as they relate to the system under consideration.

In section 5.3 I formulated that in general an EAM audience has an EAM audience goal set, a set of goals from the individual EAM audience members that the EAM is required to contribute to. The goals in this EAM audience goal set may all converge entirely, may be entirely spread out and non-overlapping, or

anything in between. Regardless, the EA modeler needs to create an EAM that maximally contributes to the EAM audience goal set as a whole. To this end, the modeler will need to formulate for themselves an *EAM objective*, which can inform the construction of the EAM in such a way that the resulting EAM will maximally contribute to the EAM audience goal set. Put in a definition:

Definition 5.13 Enterprise architecture model objective: *the objective that an enterprise architecture modeler needs to meet, in order for the enterprise architecture model to provide the maximum contribution to the goals of the enterprise architecture model audience.*

Positing the concept of an EAM objective gives rise to the following new relations:

- As section 3.5 shows objectives to contribute to goals, it must be the EA modeler’s intention that the EAM objective *contributes* to the EAM audience goal set;
- Having formulated an EAM objective, the EA modeler can know what to include in the EAM, and how. I propose that the EAM objective *informs* the EAM;
- To this end, the EA modeler needs to *pursue* the EAM objective whilst creating the EAM;
- As section 3.5 shows results to contribute to goals, and the EAM is a result, it is fair to say that the EAM itself *contributes* to the EAM audience goal set as well (to one degree or another).

An OntoUML representation of the terms and relations discussed above (as well as some discussed prior) is given in fig. 14 below.

Figure 14: OntoUML representation of how an EA modeler is pursuing an EAM objective.

5.8 How an EAM audience member judges an EAM’s quality

The quality of a product or service is determined by the perception of the consumers of that product or service (Kenyon & Sen, 2015, ch.1)¹¹. For the product that is the EAM, its quality is determined by the

¹¹Differing views of quality exist. The view espoused in Kenyon and Sen (2015) broadly follows the approach from Total Quality Management as espoused by Deming, Juran, Ishikawa, and more – see Talha (2004).

perception of its consumers: the members of the EAM audience. To capture how the EAM audience as a whole comes to a quality judgment for the EAM that they are consuming, I start from an individual EAM audience member. That member is pursuing their own particular EAM audience member goal, and to that end the EAM audience member will consume the EAM. This consumption of the EAM then leads to the EAM audience member conceiving in their mind an Architecture concept*. The EAM audience member can then engage in *consulting* this Architecture concept*. The EAM audience member can then engage in *consulting* this Architecture concept*.

(During and) after making use of the EAM, the EAM audience member will be *forming* an *EAM quality judgment* based on at least the following criteria:

- The completeness and the quality of the information that they extracted from the model;
- The ease with which this Architecture concept* can be integrated in this member’s mind;
- the extent to which this member’s understanding of the Architecture concept* actually contributes to their EAM audience member goal.

When an EAM audience member is *judging* how well the consumption of the EAM has served them, then they are judging the EAM itself. This consideration now provides the definition for *EAM quality judgment*:

Definition 5.14 Enterprise architecture model quality judgment: *the judgment by an enterprise architecture model audience member of the ease with which they can employ the information in the enterprise architecture model in the pursuit of their goal, and the extent to which their understanding of this information actually contributes to those goals.*

The graphical representation of the terms and relations discussed above is given in fig. 15. Note that in OntoUML terms the EAM quality judgment is not a <<kind>>, but a <<relator>>, signaling that it is not a functional complex, but actually the truthmaker of the material relation *judges*.

Figure 15: OntoUML representation of how an EAM audience member arrives at an EAM quality judgment.

5.9 A model for EAM quality

When describing the quality of an *EAM*, the first term that is employed is always *model quality* as a quality, characteristic, or feature that the EAM is *having*. To obtain an understanding for what this actually

entails, I turn to Kenyon and Sen (2015), who hold that any consumer that obtains a product or service “is essentially buying a bundle of attributes” (Kenyon & Sen, 2015, p.2).

To come to a somewhat more specific account, I notice that an EAM is essentially a collection of data, describing the enterprise architecture. Thus I can turn to the ISO 25012:2008(E) standard, as it offers a quality model specifically for data (International Organization for Standardization, 2008, ch.5) dubbed the “data quality model”. This conceptual model is straight-forward: quality is captured using fifteen distinct “quality characteristics”.

Note that International Organization for Standardization (2008) and Kenyon and Sen (2015) are using “characteristic” and “attribute” synonymously. I will employ the latter term. Based on the above, I can then say that *EAM quality* is an aggregation of *EAM Quality Attributes (QAs)*. Being an aggregation, the relation between the two would be *having*.

Given the above, a straightforward conceptual model in OntoUML for the quality of an EAM is shown in fig. 16. This figure shows EAM quality to be an aggregation of n QAs.

Figure 16: OntoUML representation of the conceptual model for EAM quality.

The accompanying definitions are:

Definition 5.15 *Enterprise architecture model quality attribute*: a characteristic of an enterprise architecture model that contributes to an enterprise architecture model quality judgment.

Definition 5.16 *Enterprise architecture model quality*: the aggregation of all enterprise architecture model quality attributes.

There currently is no consensus on the contents of the set of attributes that comprise EAM quality. Often ISO/IEC 25010:2011(E) (International Organization for Standardization, 2011) is used as the source for quality attributes, but this standard is meant specifically for software development, and the systems that result from that. The attributes from that standard do not carry over well to other domains, among which EAMs. An alternative could be the set of 27 attributes that I previously described in Schoonderbeek (2020). This set was compiled from the literature, but I noted there in the conclusions that the set was only an initial approximation, and not complete. That set may serve as a beginning for a more systematic investigation, but I will not initiate such an investigation in this thesis.

5.10 A summary of EAMOn terms and relations

In chapters 4 and 5 I have documented how I came to a full set of well-defined terms and their interrelations. These terms, definitions, and relations together form the applied ontology that is EAMOn. For easy reference, I have compiled table 1 shown below, which contains all the terms, and table 2 shown below, containing all the relations.

Lexical term	Definition	type
Actor	3.4	kind
Architecture concept	5.6	kind
Architecture concept*	5.9	kind
Correspondence	5.12	relator
EA modeler	5.4	role
EAM	4.19	kind
EAM audience	4.17	collective
EAM audience goal set	5.11	collective
EAM audience member	4.16	role
EAM audience member goal	5.10	kind
EAM content	5.7	kind
EAM embodiment	5.8	kind
EAM objective	5.13	kind
EAM quality	5.16	quality
EAM quality attribute	5.15	attribute
EAM quality judgment	5.14	relator
EAM universe	5.3	kind
System	5.1	kind
System universe	5.2	kind
World	5.5	kind

Table 1: Domain lexicon for enterprise architecture modeling: twenty terms, their definitions, and their OntoUML type.

Type	def.	from / to
Aggregates		EAM Universe → EAM; EAM audience → EAM audience member; EAM audience goal set → EAM audience member goal; System Universe → System; System Universe → World
Captures		EAM → Architecture Concept
Carries		EAM embodiment → EAM content
Composes		EAM → EAM content; EAM → EAM embodiment
Conceives		EA Modeler → System; EA Modeler → System Universe; EA Modeler → Architecture Concept; EAM audience member → Architecture Concept*
Constructs		EA Modeler → EAM
Consults		EA Modeler → Architecture Concept; EAM audience member → Architecture Concept*
Consumes	def. 4.2	EAM Audience Member → EAM
Contains		EAM Universe → Architecture Concept; System Universe → System; System Universe → World
Contributes		EAM → EAM audience goal set; EAM objective → EAM audience goal set
Corresponds	def. 5.12	Architecture Concept* → Architecture Concept
Expresses		EAM Embodiment → Architecture Concept
Has		EAM → EAM Quality; EAM Quality → EAM Quality Attribute
Informs		EAM Objective → EAM; System Universe → EAM Universe
Interprets		Architecture Concept* → EAM Embodiment
Is understanding		Architecture Concept* → EAM
Judges		EAM Audience Member → EAM
Matches		Architecture Concept* → EAM Content
Perceives		EA Modeler → World
Pursues		EA Modeler → EAM objective; EAM Audience → EAM Audience Goal Set; EAM audience member → EAM audience member goal
Reads		EAM Audience Member → EAM embodiment
References		Architecture Concept → System
Reflects		EAM Content → Architecture Concept
Stands for		EAM → System
Writes		EA Modeler → EAM Embodiment

Table 2: Domain lexicon for EA modeling: forty-one relations of twenty-five different types.

CHAPTER 6

Practical application of EAMOn

6.1 A first look at the practical application of EAMOn

In this chapter, I will demonstrate that [Enterprise Architecture Model Ontology \(EAMOn\)](#) is suitable for both *investigating* [Enterprise Architecture Models \(EAMs\)](#) and EAM quality, as well as *attaining* EAM quality in the practice of [Enterprise Architecture \(EA\)](#) modeling. Based on Steiner and Albert (2017, p.6), this demonstration shows that EAMOn has application validity.

- In section 6.2 I apply EAMOn, and the theory of modeling that it contains, to theorize what aspects can or will negatively influence the quality judgment of one or more of an EAM's audience members. I will indicate the use of EAMOn by referencing the relevant definitions (for terms/concepts) and figures (for relations). This demonstration shows that EAMOn is well suited to discuss and investigate EAM quality, and thus answers the research question in section 1.2.
- In section 6.3 I then use the quality aspects discussed in section 6.2 to create provisional EA modeling guidelines that positively influence the quality of an EAM. This demonstrates that EAMOn is well suited for use in the practice of EA modeling to promote EAM quality. Furthermore, this will directly provide benefits to practicing EA modelers, as these guidelines (even though their current status is provisional) can immediately be applied by them in their every day work.

Note, however, that this chapter itself serves not to *expand* EAMOn, nor the theory on which it is built. As indicated above, it is primarily a *demonstration* of the applicability of the materials developed in the previous chapters chapters 4 and 5.

Also note that EAMOn is not yet supported by means of quantitative research. Thus both the EAM quality aspects and the EA modeling guidelines are provisional, contingent on future experimental validation of EAMOn that has been relegated to future research. Nevertheless, on the assumption that EAMOn is valid, the guidelines that will be arrived at in section 6.3 must also be considered valid.

6.2 A provisional look at improving EA model quality

6.2.1 An interpretation of EA model quality

EAM quality has been defined in chapter 5 by means of a number of definitions. These are:

- EAM quality is an aggregation of EAM [Quality Attributes \(QAs\)](#) – definition 5.16;
- EAM QAs are aspects of an EAM that are involved in a quality judgment – definition 5.15;
- An EAM quality judgment is made by an EAM audience member, when they consider what they have learned from the EAM model (the Architecture concept*) – definition 5.14.

Taken together, these definitions show that an EA modeler can show to have improved an EAM's quality, if they can show to have positively affect the quality judgment of the aggregate of EAM audience members. And to achieve that, the EA modeler needs to positively influence the EAM QAs – that is to say, to positively influence relevant aspects of the EAM itself. That raises the question what these aspects could be. The following sections will attempt to address this question.

6.2.2 Phases of EA modeling

In EA, there is no generally accepted, detailed process for creating EAMs. As a consequence, even the widely accepted standard [The Open Group Architecture Framework \(TOGAF\)](#) can only advise the EA modeler to determine for themselves what the overall modeling process needs to be ([The Open Group, 2022c](#), ch.4.3.1.1). In order to apply EAMOn to EA modeling, I thus have to come to a first approximation of the EA modeling process that has sufficient detail so as to allow for the application of EAMOn concepts.

For that, I depart from the specific interpretation of the scope of EA as outlined in section 3.1. Under this interpretation, EA has an obligation to *design* the future state of the enterprise. In practice this means creating an EAM that contains a design for the future state, as well as another EAM that contains the design of the current state. These can then be compared, so as to find out what has to be changed to arrive at the desired future state. I also take as a baseline the modeling process as described in Lankhorst et al. ([2017](#), ch.7.2).

On the basis of the EAMOn model, compiled in chapter 5 and depicted throughout fig. 8 through fig. 15, the process of creating and using an EAM can be divided into the following separate phases:

1. **EA scoping:** The EA modeler assesses who will be in the EAM audience (fig. 12). From that assessment, they will formulate an EAM objective that they have reason to believe will contribute to the EAM audience goal set (fig. 14). This includes identifying which System within which System universe needs to be modeled in the EAM.
2. **EA conception:** With the EAM objective in mind, the EA modeler then will conceive of the System under consideration. This System is envisioned to live within some particular System universe, that the EA modeler also needs to conceive, in the form of the EAM universe. From the sum of these conceptions, the EA modeler then extracts and conceives the Architecture concept (fig. 9).
3. **EAM construction:** The EA modeler then consults the Architecture concept in their mind, as well as the EAM objective, and based on that constructs the EAM by writing its EAM embodiment (fig. 10).
4. **EA consumption:** When the EAM is ready for consumption, an EAM audience member consumes the EAM model by reading it, and forming in their mind an Architecture concept* (fig. 11), their own mental model of the architecture of the System under consideration. Then the EAM audience member compares what they learned from the EAM with the goals that they have (fig. 12). From this they form an EAM quality judgment (fig. 15).

Note that it is likely that the EA modeling process will not linearly progress through these phases. Instead the process will iterate through the different phases. This is exemplified by the fact that TOGAF has considered it necessary to document specific techniques for handling iteration in the EA process ([The Open Group, 2022e](#)). Further note that the phases identified above align well with the conceptual design activities from the general engineering design process ([Dieter & Schmidt, 2013](#), ch.1).

6.2.3 Influences on EAM quality

Each of the phases described in the previous section 6.2.2 involves aspects that might negatively impact the final quality judgment of the EAM by one or more EAM audience members via some QA of the EAM itself. I will use EAMOn to identify a number of these aspects for each EA modeling phase, and make use of the EAMOn lexicon and the relations from the EAMOn model to describe them.

EAM quality influences in the EA scoping phase

In the EA scoping phase, the EA modeler (definition 5.4) needs to formulate an EAM objective (definition 5.13) to pursue (fig. 10) while modeling the EAM (definition 4.19). Since this objective informs (fig. 14) the creation process of the EAM, it has a major effect on the final EAM QAs (definition 5.15).

The EA modeler first needs to determine the EAM audience's (definition 4.17) composition and properties. This comprises inventorying which Actors (definition 3.4) will be EAM audience members (definition 4.16). Then for each of the EAM audience member, the EA modeler will assess the EAM audience member goal (definition 5.10) that they pursue (fig. 12). Note that if an EA audience member is actually some form of system that consumes (fig. 11) the EAM, then there is a human Actor behind that system who is the origin of the EAM audience member goal. The (sometimes conflicting) EAM audience member goals need to be aggregated into an EAM audience goal set (definition 5.11). From that goal set, the EA modeler then can formulate the required EAM objective in such a way that it maximally contributes (fig. 14) to the EAM audience goal set.

The EAM objective also determines how to identify and delineate the System (definition 5.1) that the EAM stands for, as well as the System universe (definition 5.2) that is that System's context (fig. 8). If the EAM objective is not determined with sufficient accuracy, then the System or its delineation may be compromised, as well as the System universe.

For things like baseline architectures, that System universe can be considered the actual World (definition 5.5) we live in, and this world can readily be inspected through perception (fig. 8). But most of the time, the System universe is some future state, contingent on the choices that the decision makers in the enterprise make, as well as a host of assumptions on how the actual world has evolved to become that future state. Thus, a lack of care or attention on the part of the EA modeler when conceiving (fig. 8) of the System universe can lead to incorrect assumptions about the context of the System.

Every mistake or oversight made during these activities will result in one or more of the following:

- An EAM objective that misses out on some aspects that would have contributed (fig. 13) to the EAM audience member goal set, therefore detracting from the EAM audience member's EAM quality judgment (definition 5.14).
- Inclusion into the EAM of some aspects of the System and/or System universe that will not contribute to the EAM audience member goal set, and therefore cannot contribute to the EAM audience member's EAM quality judgment – but it would imply exerting modeling effort without benefit, thus negatively affecting [Return on Modeling Effort \(RoME\)](#) as discussed in section 4.3.
- Exclusion of the EAM of relevant parts of the System and/or of the System universe – which would mean these relevant parts will not become part of the EAM, thus cannot be understood (fig. 11) by the Architecture concept* (definition 5.9), therefore cannot add to the EAM audience member's EAM quality judgment.

EAM quality influences in the EA conception phase

In the EA conception phase, the EA modeler will attempt to conceive of the Architecture concept (definition 5.6). To illustrate the quality influences in this phase I will use this example: suppose the model objective is to model a business process for marketing product X to customer segment Y given the expectation that the organization can produce and sell product X by the end of the quarter. How well the EA modeler succeeds in conceiving an Architecture concept of the system (definition 5.1, here the business process) in its context (definition 5.2, here: next quarter when product X is ready for sale), depends on many things, only some of which are listed below:

- The EA modeler’s knowledge of the “business domain” of the System. In terms of the example: some specific knowledge of products like X, customers like Y, marketing, and processes will be required.
- The EA modeler’s percipience of the System universe as the context for the System. In the example: specific knowledge of the way the organization will differ once it starts producing X, and of the market conditions among customers like Y at the end of the quarter.
- The competency (skills, knowledge, experience) of the EA modeler in conceiving an Architecture concept (definition 5.6). In the example: is the EA modeler a competent business process modeler?
- The thoroughness with which the EA modeler is performing the conceptualization. In the example: is the EA modeler taking enough time for the conceptualization? Do they succeed in taking in the entirety of the System in its context? Are they conceptualizing to the level of detail that is expected/required by the EAM audience members?

Any lack or deficiency in the above things will result in missing or misunderstanding fundamental aspects of the System when conceiving of the Architecture concept, This in turn will mean that these fundamental aspects will not be represented correctly, or at all, in the EAM (definition 4.19). This then means that upon consumption (fig. 11) of the EAM by an EAM audience member, these fundamental aspects will not be part of the Architecture concept* (definition 5.9) of any of the EAM audience members (definition 4.16), therefore cannot add to the EAM audience member’s EAM quality judgment (definition 5.14).

EAM quality influences in the EAM construction phase

In the EAM construction phase, the EA modeler will have to translate the components of the Architecture concept (definition 5.6) that they hold in their head into statements that they can enter into the EAM (fig. 10). What a “statement” here means depends on the form of EAM embodiment (definition 5.8) that the EA modeler has chosen. For example: if the model is expressed in natural language such as English, then a statement will be a sentence, or a collection of several sentences. If the model is expressed in a formal modeling language such as ArchiMate, then a statement will be a single element or relation, or a combination thereof (The Open Group, 2022a, fig.1).

There are two ways in which the EA modeler is influencing the EAM itself:

1. The EA modeler writes (fig. 10) the statement that they believe describe the Architecture concept that they hold in their mind.
2. By their writing the model, the EA modeler indirectly creates the EAM content (definition 5.7) that the EAM embodiment (definition 5.8) is carrying (fig. 10). The aim is to have this EAM content reflect (fig. 13) the Architecture concept as well as possible.

For the process of directly writing the EAM: any error in correctly transcribing the Architecture concept (including syntax, inappropriate modeling language, incorrect use of modeling conventions, visualization, et cetera) will lead to the loss of information for the EAM to carry (fig. 10), or the loss of clarity for the EAM audience member reading (fig. 11) the EAM. Both can negatively influence the Architecture concept* (definition 5.9) that an EAM audience member conceives (fig. 11), thereby detracting from the EAM audience member’s EAM quality judgment (fig. 15).

For the process of indirectly creating EAM content: the use of incomplete or ambiguous labels and descriptions, incorrect level of precision, incorrect use of modeling language constructs, or even insufficient knowledge of the discipline of EA itself, will detract from how the EAM content (definition 5.7) will reflect (fig. 13) the Architecture concept (definition 5.6) that the EA modeler is attempting to present. This also negatively influences the Architecture concept* that an EAM audience member conceives, thereby detracting from the EAM audience member’s EAM quality judgment.

EAM quality influences in the EAM consumption phase

In the EAM consumption phase the model is being consumed (fig. 11) by an individual EAM audience member (definition 4.16). This process is out of the hands of the EA modeler. Some of the problems that might occur in this phase are:

- The EAM does insufficiently or not at all contribute (fig. 14) to the EAM audience member goal that an EAM audience member pursues (fig. 12);
- An EAM audience member lacks the background knowledge to correctly interpret some part of the EAM embodiment (definition 5.8) such as a concept, relation, visualization, or formulation – consequently the Architecture concept* (definition 5.9) of the EAM audience member does not sufficiently match (fig. 13) the EAM content (definition 5.7). Note that the EAM audience member may not notice this at the time of consuming the EAM, but when the mismatch between their Architecture concept* and the actual architecture of the System becomes apparent, they will revise their EAM quality judgment accordingly, as the perception of quality is dynamic (Kenyon & Sen, 2015, ch.1, ch17.2).
- An EAM audience member cannot read (fig. 11) the modeling language used to write (fig. 10) the EAM embodiment.

Each of these problems will detract from the EAM audience member's quality judgment.

From the previous texts in this section it should be clear that these problems could potentially have foreseen by the EA modeler. Thus, it is the responsibility of the EA modeler to anticipate and mitigate such problems in the prior phases.

6.3 Provisional EA modeling guidelines derived from EAMOn

Based on the quality influences described above in section 6.2, I can now provisionally formulate a number of practical EA modeling guidelines that will assist an EA modeler in achieving higher quality EAMs – that is: EA models for which the EAM audience members will make a positive EAM quality judgment (definition 5.14). As noted in section 6.1, these guidelines are provisional, subject to empirical validation in follow-up research. To connect these provisional guidelines to the existing EA modeling practice, I will connect the guidelines where possible to TOGAF (The Open Group, n.d.), as that is the the most prevalent EA methodology, as even its detractors acknowledge (Kotusev, 2018, ch.2.2).

6.3.1 Determine the model audience and their goals

When beginning work on an EAM, the EA modeler will usually start from some sort of assignment (in whatever form). Independent from who fulfills the EA modeler role (definition 5.4; an enterprise architect, some other architecture professional working in an EA team, or yet someone else), the assignment should contain enough information, implicitly or explicitly, to establish what needs to be modeled, what for, and for who.

As not every stakeholder will be required and/or be able to consume the EAM (section 4.5), the EA modeler needs to determine who these EAM audience members are, so as to be able to obtain an understanding of the goals that each EAM audience member has for the EAM. EAMOn refers to this in fig. 12.

Guideline 1 – Identify the Enterprise architecture model audience members: *Explicitly determine the actors that the enterprise architecture model is intended to serve. Record these actors with the enterprise architecture itself.*

Note the use of the verb *intending* in the guideline: the EA modeler does not have to know *with certainty* that *every* EAM audience member will *actually* consume the model. But for any actor in the EAM audience, it should be the case that they *can* consume the EAM, and that consuming it *will* contribute to their goals.

If a person who was *not* identified as an EAM audience member is dissatisfied with the EAM, then this does not indicate that the EAM is of insufficient quality. Instead, it is either a failure of the EA modeler to include this person in the EAM audience, or it is a misapprehension of the person in question that the EAM can be expected to serve them.

Having identified the EAM audience members, the EA modeler should then proceed to inventory the goals that each of them has, to which the EAM is supposed to contribute. This inventorying may take place by directly asking each of them, or inferring their goals from written requests or assignments, their roles in the organization, their stated strategy, other comments or statements, or any other indirect means. Also note that the EAM audience member may not be able to (fully) articulate their goals and expectations. In many instances, the EAM audience member as a stakeholder simply experiences concerns or needs, and it is up to an enterprise architect to correctly identify and express this concern ([International Organization for Standardization, 2022a](#), ch.5.2.3).

The importance of determining these goals cannot be overstated: if the EA modeler does not know what an EAM audience member expects from the EAM, then having the EAM fulfilling these expectations becomes a matter of chance. Thus I formulate the following guideline:

Guideline 2 – Establish the Enterprise architecture model audience goal set: *Determine for each of the Enterprise architecture model audience members the goal or goals that the enterprise architecture model is intended to serve. Prioritize these goals, and for contradictory goals select which one overrides the other. Then aggregate these individual goals into a single larger goal, or set thereof,*

A TOGAF instrument that can assist in these matters is the Business Scenario ([The Open Group, 2022f](#)), as it can help uncover stakeholders and their goals. Although as mentioned: not every stakeholder is necessarily an EAM audience member.

6.3.2 Determine the system and the system universe

Another task to be performed before starting on the EAM is to determine what comprises the System that is the referent for the EAM to be constructed, as well as what the System universe is in which that System is positioned. For this, the EA modeler usually can consult either the modeling assignment or the sponsor of the modeling assignment. A TOGAF deliverable that can assist here is the Architecture Vision ([The Open Group, 2022b](#), ch.4.2.8).

Conventional modeling wisdom, such as the referenced TOGAF Architecture Vision, already recommends explicitly determining the referent of the model (usually in terms like “scope”). However, as mentioned in section 6.2.2: explicitly paying attention to the System universe will bring more advantages to the modeling process than when the EA modeler would just focus on the “scope” as a delineation of the System under consideration. This is because the System universe interacts with the System, and is the foundation for determining the required level of domain knowledge, as well as background knowledge that the EAM audience members are required to have in order to understand (the architecture of) the System itself. The System universe informs the Modeling universe; from their investigation of the System universe, the EA modeler will construct the Model universe, which itself is the context for the EAM. This can be inferred from EAMOn, especially figs. 8 and 9.

These observations give rise to the following guidelines:

Guideline 3 – System: *Identify the system that the enterprise architecture model is representing, specifically its boundaries. Record the identification and boundaries of the system with the enterprise architecture itself.*

Guideline 4 – System universe: *Explicitly define and label the System universe for which the enterprise architecture model is being drafted.*

6.3.3 Establish the model objective

As discussed in section 5.7, the goals of the individual members of an EAM audience are not guaranteed to be identical, nor do they automatically form a coherent set. Therefore the total set of these goals (the EAM audience goal set, definition 5.11) cannot be used directly to inform what to include in the EAM, and how to express that information. Instead, the modeler needs to compile, curate, and evaluate the EAM audience member goal set, and based on that goal set formulate a single EAM objective. This objective will then inform what and how to model the system under consideration, as is shown in fig. 14.

However, as some EAM audience member goals may be incompatible, it is important to not only determine what the EAM objective must be, but also to communicate this EAM objective to the EAM audience. In this way, if an EAM audience member does not see the EAM (sufficiently) contributing to their goal, they can verify if this is because the EAM is somehow falling short, or if the EAM simply has not been geared to (fully) contribute towards their goal. Additionally, recording the EAM objective with the EAM will be helpful when someone from outside the EAM audience considers consuming the EAM. And finally, recording the EAM objective with the EAM itself will also assist in future reuse of the EAM.

Thus I come to the following guideline:

Guideline 5 – Enterprise architecture model objective: *Establish the objective that the enterprise architecture model is intended to achieve. Record this objective with the enterprise architecture model itself.*

6.3.4 Establish the EAM Universe

The EA modeler must decide not just on what needs to go into the EAM, but also about what can safely be left out. For this, they need to know not only what aspects of the system to be modeled are relevant to achieve the EAM objective, but also what aspects *outside* of the system itself are relevant to that objective. This includes making explicit the aspects of the system universe that differ from what an EAM audience member may expect (see fig. 8 in particular). To be able to identify these aspects, the EA modeler needs to establish in their mind a sufficiently clear representation of the System universe (definition 5.2, in the form of an EAM universe (definition 5.3). In TOGAF, this concept can be recognized for example in the Business Scenario, where it takes the form of “the business and technical environment” ([The Open Group, 2022f](#), ch.7.2.2),

Having established the EAM universe, the EA modeler can recognize in this EAM universe pertinent aspects that manifest outside of the system to be modeled. The EA modeler now has two ways to deal with these:

- Explicitly adding to the EAM representations those particular aspects.
- Providing with the EAM an explicit description of the context of the EAM, so that the particular aspects are sufficiently clear to the EAM audience members. This context is the pertinent part of the EAM universe.

The first way boils down to straightforward EA modeling. The second way amounts to creating what amounts to a new, separate model of the EAM universe itself. For this, EAMON and the modeling guidelines in this section 6.3 recursively apply.

As with the prior guideline 5, recording the EAM universe will also assist in future reuse of the EAM. Its main advantage is that it may signal that an EAM created in the past may not readily be reused in the present, if the EAM universe for the system of interest has significantly changed.

I capture the above in the following, strongly recommended guideline:

Guideline 6 – Enterprise architecture model universe: *From the system universe, derive what the relevant context (the enterprise architecture model universe) for the enterprise architecture model is. Record this context with the enterprise architecture model itself.*

6.3.5 Determine the EAM embodiment

Every EAM audience member will need to be able to read (fig. 11) the EAM embodiment, and then interpret (fig. 13) it to come to their own conceptualization of the architecture: the Architecture concept*. Therefore, the EAM embodiment must not only be suitable to express the Architecture concept that the EA modeler wishes to convey to the EAM audience members, but also be suitable for consumption by those EAM audience members.

Given this, the EA modeler is responsible for selecting a type of EAM embodiment that can actually satisfy these demands. This entails selecting a suitable modeling form (static model, dynamic model, diagram, program, et cetera) and accompanying modeling language (natural language, formal modeling language, programming language, et cetera). The model must also be published or distributed via one or more channels (web site, file share, modeling tool, et cetera) so that every EAM audience member can actually access the EAM.

All of these choices and more, need to be made by the EA modeler to ensure that the EAM audience members will be able to consume the EAM. This leads to the following recommendation:

Guideline 7 – Enterprise architecture model embodiment: *Select the type of enterprise architecture model embodiment that can achieve the enterprise architecture model objective, and can be consumed by every one of the enterprise architecture model audience members.*

6.3.6 Construct the actual EAM

When the EA modeler starts to construct the actual EAM, then EAMON allows for describing specific aspects for this phase that can influence the EAM quality judgment by the EAM audience members, in both the positive and negative sense. These aspects are labeled QAs (definition 5.15), and I have compiled a full set of these before in Schoonderbeek (2020). However, I designated the set of QAs in that bachelor thesis as “only a first approximation that cannot be considered complete” (Schoonderbeek, 2020, p.37).

The analysis of the construction phase of the EAM from section 6.2 indicates that EAMON can be used effectively to investigate EAM model quality. But it does not yet provide sufficient insights so as to be able to construct specific modeling guidelines for this phase, so I have to relegate the drafting of such guidelines to future work.

6.3.7 Present the EAM to the model audience members with its metadata

In the previous guidelines 1, 3, 5 and 6, I have advised that different pieces of information gathered in the EA modeling process should be recorded with the EAM itself. These are pieces of information that are *not* describing the enterprise architecture of the system itself, instead they are about the EAM and its use. Thus each of these pieces of information are metadata (International Organization for Standardization, 2023, p. 3.2.26).

There may also be other pieces of metadata that are of value, depending on your organization's processes and standards for EA model management. This additional metadata could include, but is not limited to:

- Status of the model. For example: draft, approved, deprecated, superseded.
- Date of last status change.
- Owner of the model. For example: Chief Operating Officer.
- Author of the model.
- Last revision date of the model.
- The stakeholders for which the model has been drafted. The list should include at a minimum all the EAM audience members, but will most likely also include people who have an interest in the system but are not expected to consume the EAM independent from the enterprise architect – or at all.
- Enterprise Metadata model used to draft the EAM ([The Open Group, 2022b](#), ch.1.2.3).
- Audit trails for all the above.

Collecting and managing some of these data may seem like overkill when an EA initiative is of limited time span. But when the initiative spans a longer time, or when the EAM is to be (re)used after a long period, then this data becomes increasingly more valuable. Thus I formulate the following guideline, spanning both the metadata mentioned in the other guidelines, and the additional metadata in the list above:

Guideline 8 – Model metadata: *Explicitly record an enterprise architecture model's metadata, and include it in or with the model.*

6.3.8 Discussing the formulated guidelines

The eight guidelines formulated in this section 6.3 can be compared with guidelines proffered in research and in professional literature. Note that the guidelines I formulated are geared toward *how* to model, providing advice on what to do when creating an EAM, independent from the pertinent EA domain, system under consideration, modeling language, or scope. Not all sets of guidelines follow this tack; some focuses on what the result, the model, should be (such as Sandkuhl et al. (2014, ch.12.2)). However, Lankhorst et al. (2017) is suitable for comparison, as it presents guidelines geared toward how to model. These guidelines have been created based on interviews with architects, combined with the experience of the authors and information from literature, and thus reflect enterprise architecture practice.

When I compare the guidelines that arise from EAMON with the maxims and guidelines from Lankhorst et al., I find the following:

- Guideline 1: this guideline reflects the concept of a “system development community” as outlined in Lankhorst et al. (2017, ch.4.2.1). Note that in that concept, there does not seem to be a distinction between those in that community that (help) create the model, and those that do not, but have a concern or stake in the system being developed.
- Guidelines 2 and 5: Lankhorst et al. (2017, ch.7.3) has both the guideline “A model has to provide answers to questions” and a maxim of relevance “be relevant (i.e. model things related to the modelling goal)”. Comparing my two guidelines to the guideline and maxim from Lankhorst et al., I believe the EAMON-derived guidelines are more detailed and precise, while the correspondence lends credence to the EAMON-based result.
- Guidelines 3 and 4: Lankhorst et al. do not offer a guideline that is comparable to mine, but do describe under “basing modeling activities” (Lankhorst et al., 2017, ch.7.2.2) that the EA modeler needs to “establish the purpose, scope and focus” for the model. This description covers the same ground as my two guidelines 3 and 4.
- Guideline 6: I have not found any guideline in Lankhorst et al. (2017) that explicitly references the *context* of the model.

- Guideline 7: in contrast with the previous guideline, this one is reflected throughout the entirety of Lankhorst et al. (2017, ch.7). This is not unexpected, as it is intended to provide guidance in the application of ArchiMate 3.0, an EA modeling language.
- Guideline 8: While Lankhorst et al. (2017) recognizes the need to collect some of the data I have not found any guideline that deals with explicitly recording this data with the model.

This cursory comparison between EAMOn and EA practice-oriented advice from Lankhorst et al. suggests that the guidelines that were derived using EAMOn align well with EA practice. But as guidelines 6 and 8 have no peer in Lankhorst et al. (2017), it also indicates that application of EAMOn can bring novel insights into the practice of EA modeling.

To ensure the practical relevance for the applied ontology that is [Enterprise Architecture Model Ontology \(EAMOn\)](#) for the knowledge domain of [Enterprise Architecture Model \(EAM\)](#) for which it was drafted, EAMOn needs to be validated. For this, [\(Steiner & Albert, 2017\)](#) proffers two types of validation, both of which I will perform for EAMOn:

- The ontology needs to be well built. For this I have performed both an ontological analysis, and a check against a database with guidelines for ontology construction.
- The ontology needs to actually be applicable in the knowledge domain for which it was drafted. For this I can use the results from section 6.1.

7.1 Ontological analysis: capturing EAMOn in OntoUML

The first step in validating [EAMOn](#) is performing an ontological analysis, by encoding the ontology in OntoUML. For this, I have entered EAMOn in a specialized modeling tool. This encoding allows for two specific tests:

- A successful mapping of the terms onto OntoUML classes shows that the concepts identified in EAMOn have a sound ontological foundation, as described in [Unified Foundational Ontology \(UFO\)](#) [\(Guizzardi, 2005\)](#).
- The used OntoUML plug-in can provide an analysis that identifies syntactical issues with the OntoUML model¹².

In chapters 4 and 5 I drafted the domain lexicon, and for every set of terms I introduced, I also posited their interrelations. I then modeled the terms and relations in an OntoUML model¹³. Every term has then been mapped to an OntoUML concept, as shown in fig. 8 through fig. 16. This demonstrates that each of the terms have a sound ontological foundation in UFO.

Furthermore, the OntoUML plugin used to create the OntoUML model for EAMOn has a built-in syntax checker that can report on the correctness of the model. For the EAMOn OntoUML model, the plugin reports no syntactical issues. This fact evinces syntactical correctness.

Thus, these two tests of the ontological analysis provide a good indication that EAMOn is well built.

¹²See the plugin documentation at <https://github.com/OntoUML/ontouml-vp-plugin>.

¹³The OntoUML model can be downloaded from this link: https://janschoonderbeek.nl/download/en/EAMOn_v1/EAMOn_v1.00.vpp. To open it, use Visual Paradigm v17.0 or higher, with the OntoUML plugin 0.5.3 or higher installed.

7.2 Using the Ontology Pitfall Scanner! (Oops!)

A second step of content validation concerns the use of a practical set of ontology guidelines. For this I make use of the OOPS! catalog, described in Poveda-Villalón et al. (2014). Of the forty-one pitfalls listed there, sixteen pertain to EAMOn in its current form. The other pitfalls are not relevant, as they deal specifically with ontologies that contain properties, are encoded in OWL, are published online, or are part of a linked data effort. EAMOn does not have these characteristics.

In the list below, each relevant pitfall is listed along with a terse description from OOPS!’s web site (Villalón, 2021), followed by the measures I took to avoid it:

- P01. Creating polysemous elements: An ontology element (class, object property or datatype property) whose identifier has different senses is included in the ontology to represent more than one conceptual idea or property;
- P03. Creating the relationship “is” instead of using “rdfs:subClassOf”, “rdf:type” or “owl:sameAs”;
- P07. Merging different concepts in the same class: A class whose name refers to two or more different concepts is created.

I formulated my naming conventions (section 3.3) to explicitly avoid homonymy and polysemy, including common and generic verbs. I did not employ the label *is*, nor conjugations of it.

- P02. Creating synonyms as classes: Several classes whose identifiers are synonyms are created and defined as equivalent (owl:equivalentClass) in the same namespace.

Since I methodically progressed through the definition of each class in table 1, I have created no classes that are equivalent.

- P04. Creating unconnected ontology elements: Ontology elements (classes, object properties and datatype properties) are created isolated, with no relation to the rest of the ontology.

EAMOn is fully captured in the nine figures 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16. All of these are connected via the $\langle\langle\text{kind}\rangle\rangle$ *EAM*, except for 9 and 12, but the former is connected to 8 via *System*, and the latter to 11 via *EAM audience member*. Thus, all elements are related into one single group.

- P05. Defining wrong inverse relationships: Two relationships are defined as inverse relations when they are not necessarily inverse;

P06. Including cycles in a class hierarchy: A cycle appears when some class A has a subclass (directly or indirectly) B, and at the same time B is a superclass (directly or indirectly) of A;

P17. Overspecializing a hierarchy: The hierarchy in the ontology is specialized in such a way that the final leaves are defined as classes and these classes will not have instances;

P21. Using a miscellaneous class: This refers to the creation of a class with the only goal of classifying the instances that do not belong to any of its sibling classes (classes with which the miscellaneous problematic class shares a common direct ancestor).

EAMOn does not include any inverse relation, subclass, nor hierarchy, nor miscellaneous class.

- P09. Missing domain information: Part of the information needed for modeling the intended domain is not included in the ontology.

The analysis by which I formulated EAMON has put down a foundation that is itself complete for the intended domain – this has been shown to be the case in the preceding chapter 6. I do recognize that this foundation is for a domain of limited scope. For instance, I have yet to address modeling with multiple EA modelers. I intend to increase the scope of EAMON in a PhD track.

- P10. Missing disjointness: The ontology lacks disjoint axioms between classes or between properties that should be defined as disjoint.

The terms in EAMON do not include sets of disjoint terms, so disjoint axioms are not required.

- P22. Using different naming conventions in the ontology: The ontology elements are not named following the same convention.

A single naming convention has been provided in section 3.3, and followed throughout this thesis.

- P24. Using recursive definitions: An ontology element (a class, an object property or a datatype property) is used in its own definition.

Every definition has been created using the method described in A.2, specifically the criteria for definitions. Recursion, whereby the definiendum appears (directly or indirectly) in the definiendum, does not occur.

- P25. Defining a relationship as inverse to itself:

EAMON has only a limited set of inverse relations. For each of these, the inverse relation has a different name. Therefore, this pitfall is avoided.

- P32. Several classes with the same label: Two or more classes have the same content for natural language annotations for naming.

Table 1 shows that every term (label) appears only once.

This analysis shows that in the creation of EAMON I have avoided the common problems (“pitfalls”) that may occur in ontology development.

7.3 Applicability of EAMON in practice

To demonstrate application validity for EAMON, Steiner and Albert (2017, ch.2.2) suggest that the best way for evaluating an ontology is the application of that ontology for the domain for which it has been created. This application in practice addresses the question whether a drafted ontology can serve the goal for which it has been created.

As EAMON has been drafted for both research into EA modeling and for use in the practice of EA modeling, ideally application of EAMON would be tested among both:

- In EAM quality research, under a representative group of EAM quality researchers;
- In EA modeling practice, under a representative group of EA modeling professionals, such as experienced and practicing enterprise architects.

However, I estimate that the latter, when performed with sufficient scientific rigor, presents a workload of at least several months. I was not able to add a workload of that size to my master program, so this

validation necessarily must be relegated to future work. Performing the former under EAM quality researcher may present a somewhat lighter workload, but this too was not feasible within the scope of a master project. I do aim to take on both of these tasks in my future doctoral work.

However, chapter 6 presents a first approximation of application of EAMOn in EAM quality research. Using EAMOn to formulate guidelines, and then cross-checking these with practical guidelines gives an indication of practical applicability, and may serve as a template for a future initiative whereby EAMOn is employed. I therefore conclude that a first, cursory test of application validity has been completed satisfactory.

CHAPTER 8

Results and Discussion

8.1 Results

I have in this thesis methodically investigated the domain of [Enterprise Architecture \(EA\)](#) modeling and of [Enterprise Architecture Model \(EAM\)](#) quality, making use of solid theoretical foundations. In chapters 4 and 5 this has yielded twenty domain-specific concepts, each with a formal definition. These concepts have been compiled in table 1 in section 5.10.

Between the defined concepts, I have drafted forty-one relations relevant for the domain of EA modeling, each of which has been labeled and described in chapters 4 and 5. For two of these relations, I have also drafted a formal definition. The relations, with the two definitions, are summarily listed in table 2 in section 5.10.

The terms and relations together are displayed in the nine figures 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, and 16. Taken together, these figures constitute a single OntoUML model

The concepts, relations, and OntoUML constitute an applied ontology for the domain of EA modeling and EAM quality. I have labeled this ontology [Enterprise Architecture Model Ontology \(EAMOn\)](#).

EAMOn has undergone two checks to ensure content validity, demonstrating that the ontology is well built. I have also taken a first look at applying the ontology to the practice of EA modeling, and investigating [EAM](#) quality. This suggests application validity, indicating that the ontology is capable to serve its intended purpose. Note that the application validity of EAMOn is provisional, contingent on experimental validation in practice.

Based on the results, it is justified to state that EAMOn is a viable answer for the research question “what constitutes a suitable ontology for investigating enterprise architecture model quality?” that I posed in chapter 1. The applied ontology that is EAMOn has practical value for researchers of EA models and EAM quality. Not only does it enable the researchers to unambiguously identify components of EAMs and of EAM quality, but it also provides a foundation for a theory of modeling based on Concept Theory. Section 6.2 can serve as an illustration on how EAMOn assists in discussing EAM model quality aspects.

EAMOn also makes it possible to create guidance for EA practitioners. I have demonstrated this in section 6.3 by provisionally drafting modeling guidelines. These guidelines can provisionally be used in the practice of EA modeling, awaiting experimental validation of EAMOn. And as with the EA researchers, EA modelers among themselves can use EAMOn concepts and terms to discuss and develop their models.

In summary: EAMOn has the potential to further the field of EAM research, and additionally to provide support for practicing EA modelers. In this way, my thesis may assist in opening minds to impact the world.

8.2 Critical evaluation

In this section I evaluate the thesis as a whole, identifying potential weaknesses and addressing possible critiques. For this, I formulate objections that a detractor could raise against EAMOn as a result, or the method by which I arrived at that result. I then attempt to address each objection.

The ontology is drafted for a specific interpretation of enterprise architecture

As declared in section 3.1, this thesis assumes that EAMs are created under a specific interpretation of the term EA. This leaves open the question of the suitability and applicability of EAMOn when the EA modeler follows a different school of thought (Lapalme, 2012).

The three different schools of EA identified by Lapalme indeed have different scopes and goals. This means that different types of EAMs are being produced, and these EAMs are used in different ways and for different audiences. However, I believe that these differences have no material influence on the ontology. I expect that experimental testing of EAMOn in organizations and with EA practitioners will show the same findings, whether the subjects follow the Enterprise Integrating school of EA that I used as the context for EAM, or another. But this indeed has to be verified with future research.

The ontology is limited

At twenty terms, the size of the lexicon (table 1) is quite limited. And of the forty-one relations (table 2), only two have a formal definition (*consuming*, definition 4.2, and *corresponding*, definition 5.12).

Despite the modest number of terms and relations in EAMOn, section 6.2 shows that EAMOn can support discussion of EAMs and EAM quality over quite a wide range of topics and areas within the domain of EA modeling. Nevertheless, as mentioned in section 2.3, an ontology is always subject to maintenance and evolution (Kendall & McGuinness, 2019). While I believe EAMOn can already be employed to great effect, I fully expect the ontology to change and grow – probably substantially. Some future work that can achieve this will be discussed in section 8.3.

The ontology is derived from “domain model”

In chapter 4, the assumption is made that the concept of a domain model is a suitable superordinate concept for an EAM, since no suitable hierarchy of model categories exists that can point to a concept that is closer. But this does not mean that no such concept exists. And since (International Organization for Standardization, 2022b) prescribes the use of “the immediate superordinate concept”, it is necessary to develop a hierarchy of model categories and expose the concepts between “domain model” and “enterprise architecture model”, so as to investigate their delimiting characteristics.

In the course of my thesis work, I have already developed significant parts of the required hierarchy of model categories. But some major shortcomings discovered late in the process prevent me from including the hierarchy at present time. However, based on the work performed so far, I am confident that the hierarchy, once developed in my PhD program, will not detract from the results obtained in this thesis – at the most I foresee some extra essential characteristics to enter the definition of EAM, and from there the ontology itself.

The ontology has not been validated using quantitative methods

An acute criticism one can leverage against EAMOn is that it currently is lacking in experimental validation in the practice of EA modeling, as noted in sections 6.1 and 6.2.

This criticism is valid, and of all possible criticisms I feel it is the most important one. The addition of experimental evaluation to this thesis (assuming it would not invalidate the ontology) would have made EAMOn that much more valuable. Unfortunately the constraints on time and effort available for a thesis project, and size of the thesis itself, precluded such an addition. Consequently, experimental validation is relegated to follow-up research, which I intend to conduct myself in a PhD research program.

The ontology only accounts for a modeler working in isolation

While the ontology accounts for differing model audience members, it does currently not deal with a situation in which multiple modelers work on a single EAM. In that situation, could the modelers have a shared, identical conception of the architecture? A single *architecture concept*? Probably not - but what does that mean for the creation of an EAM? This is not covered in this thesis, and thus EAMOn currently offers no terms or relations with which to express cooperation between EA modelers. This must be a topic for follow-up research.

The ontology assumes a single system universe

In EA, it is customary to create views that combine the baseline architecture and target architecture, so as to be able to highlight the changes that the EA initiative is concerned with. However, the assumptions and definitions used in the ontology presuppose that the EAM concerns a single system, located in a single system universe. By that light, any combination of baseline architecture and target architecture is looking at the same system in two different system universes.

I can see at least two different ways to tackle this issue. One could say that the baseline architecture and the target architecture are two different models, and subsequently that the combination in a single view is a new, third model. But that raises the question what would be the system universe of this model. Another approach would be to recognize that the view is concerning two different models, and thus label that view as a “mixed model”. This then raises the question what such a mixed model then entails. Either way, I currently have no answer for this conundrum; another topic for follow-up research.

A specific version of Concept Theory has been employed

A criticism that can be raised against EAMOn is that it leans on a specific version of concept theory (Dahlberg, 1978). Other versions exist that align with different epistemic positions (Hjørland, 2009). Employing a different version may well lead to a different ontology.

This is a valid point. EAMs deal with knowledge (about the EA), and thus any theory on EAMs needs to take epistemology into consideration. I believe that the stance of critical realism aligns well with the Concept Theory proffered by (Dahlberg, 1978), and this version has in the 45 years since its publication not received significant critique¹⁴. Nevertheless, further work is needed both to strengthen the position that application of Dahlberg’s Concept Theory in EAMOn is warranted. Furthermore, it may also be of interest to look for alternative versions of Concept Theory that work well with other epistemic stances than critical realism. The former will certainly be part of my ongoing work; I hope the latter will be taken on by colleagues in the field.

¹⁴I have attempted to find detractors for Dahlberg’s theory by using the query <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?cites=9201801910162166015>. But as of May 1st 2023, the 299 results of this query, sorted by relevance, showed no critique among the first forty hits. Nor has Dahlberg published a fundamentally different version or significant update of Dahlberg (1978).

A positivist's appreciation of the transfer of Architecture

As stated in section 3.2, my interpretation of the transfer of architecture from modeler to a model audience member via an EAM is built upon the epistemic stance of critical realism. A positivist could argue that the capture of knowledge in the form of the *architecture* concept in the EA modeler's mind can be perfect, and that the transfer to an EAM audience member could therefore conceivably also be perfect, negating any difference between *Architecture concept* (definition 5.6) and *Architecture concept** (definition 5.9).

It is my position that the transfer of the Architecture concept from the EA modeler to an EAM audience member can be imperfect even on positivism, because the EAM itself is an object in reality that can be flawed. A positivist must accept this, because the alternative would be to say that a flawed model could still transfer an idea without loss of information; pushed to its extreme, that would indicate that no amount of corruption could interfere with the transfer of information about the architecture concept, which is an untenable position.

The set of criteria that an EAM audience member uses to judge an EAM is arbitrary

In section 5.8 I posit some criteria, stating that an EAM audience member will *at least* use these criteria to judge the quality of an EAM that he has consumed. However, the list as provided in section 5.8 is both unsubstantiated and incomplete.

This is another valid point of criticism. However, research into the quality of EAMs is not only scarce (as noted in section 1.1), it is also marred by the fact that no suitable ontology is generally available (section 1.2). So the origin of this point of criticism is a chicken-and-egg situation. To solve this situation, we would first need some ontology with which to describe EAMs and EAM quality – which is precisely the topic of this thesis.

Once EAMOn is sufficiently established (meaning experimental validation and incremental improvements), it becomes possible to conduct research into EAM audience member's quality judgments and express the outcomes in concepts from EAMOn. This may lead to new or improved understanding of EAM audience member quality judgments. In turn this implicates that the wording of definition 5.14 may need to change, to reflect such a new understanding. Thus, the list of criteria from section 5.8, and the wording of definition 5.14, are only a first approximation. As always: more research is required, and I hope to conduct some of this research as a follow-up to this master thesis.

The set of criteria that an EAM audience member uses to judge an EAM goes beyond its quality attributes

Section 5.9 limits the interpretation of quality of an EAM to [Quality Attributes \(QAs\)](#) of the model itself, but in practice there are more aspects that influence how a stakeholder experiences the use of EA, and thus comes to a quality judgment.

I counter this objection as follows: suppose the EA modeler shows documentation to the EAM audience member that indicates that the EAM has been created under strict discipline. This may positively influence the EAM audience member's overall satisfaction with the resulting EAM. However, this does in no way mean that EAM quality *itself* is actually improved. What this indicates is that the EAM audience member actually executes multiple quality judgments (separate, in tandem, or otherwise), only one of which corresponds with the quality judgment on the EAM *per se* that EAMOn addresses. One could say that the quality judgment that improves by providing EA modeling documentation could be labeled an "EA process quality judgment", that exists separate from the EA model quality judgment.

8.3 Further work

I see several avenues of research that will help address the issues recorded in section 8.2 and elsewhere, and have the potential to further develop and expand EAMOn:

- As noted, the ontology currently supports a single EA modeler working on creating the EAM. As in practice modelers often work together in creating a single EAM, the ontology must be expanded, and the theory of modeling adapted, to allow for multiple EA modelers.
- As noted in section 8.2 above, an important part of the basis of the ontology is the definition for *EAM* (definition 4.19) as derived from the definition of *domain model* (definition 4.1). But as also noted, the definition for EAM should be derived from an *immediate* superordinate concept. For this, a hierarchy of model categories needs to be developed, from which a suitable immediate superordinate concept can be drawn. In the course of developing this thesis I have already created a candidate for such a hierarchy, but this needs to be developed further before it can be employed.
- In its current form, EAMOn has been drafted for the domain of Enterprise Architecture. However, I believe that it is amenable to expansion to a larger knowledge domain, containing more categories of models than just EAMs. Following the construction of the hierarchy of model categories, EAMOn presumably can be tested and expanded to envelop such other categories of models as well.
- The ontology can be used as-is to analyze an actual EA model, preferably involving both the EA modeler and some members of the EA model audience. Such an analysis will provide a test of EAMOn's application validity. I also expect that it will provide insights in what aspects of the EA model contribute to a greater or lesser extent to its quality, and what measures could be taken to guard or improve model quality.
- The ontology can be expanded with research into the relationships that are the truthmakers for the identified relations between the different terms of the ontology.
- Using this ontology, specific EA model quality attributes can be identified and documented.
- Several model quality frameworks, such as CMQF (Nelson et al., 2011), have been proposed. A validated model quality framework can provide a systematic structure to categorize and evaluate quality attributes (Lindland et al., 1994). The ontology can be employed to assist in validating these frameworks.
- Based on the theory of modeling that arose in the drafting of the ontology, it is possible to create more, and more detailed, modeling guidelines for EA modelers that will positively impact model quality.
- The ontology can be employed in research into RoME, as it provides (for the domain of Enterprise Architecture) an extra footing for both the definition of modeling effort, and for the determination what value an EA model brings.

I conclude by noting that I believe that every bit of additional work will uncover new and rich avenues of exploration, each of which will directly or indirectly lead to tangible improvements in the understanding of modeling and the application of models. This has the potential of significantly improving the modeling practices of tens of thousands of professionals the world over, and I very much look forward to see the results of this future work.

APPENDIX A

Drafting definitions

A.1 Types of definitions

A major part of any ontology consists of determining formal names and definitions for the knowledge domain under consideration. But there does not seem to be an agreed-upon definition for the term *definition* itself (Moore, 2009). Consequentially, there are different ways by which definitions are drafted. International Organization for Standardization (2022b), Moore (2009), and Saenz et al. (2009) indicate that different kinds of definitions are:

- *denotative* or *ostensive*, whereby denoting a number of examples serves to convey the full extension of the definition;
- *synonymous*, an intentional method whereby a number of (sometimes partial) synonyms are intended to convey the meaning of the definition;
- *operational*, which solely use a set of criteria;
- *analytical*, also known as *connotation* or as *genus and differentia*. This intensional method uses classification by starting from a more general concept (the genus) that shares characteristics and is well understood, and then stating attributes or characteristics (the differentia) that set apart the more specific subject of the definition from that general concept. The way to come to an analytical definition is presented as breaking down the term to be defined, the definiendum, into its constituent elements. When taken together, these elements then constitute the definiens, the expression of the definition;
- *synthesis*, whereby the whole of the relationships of some concept to other concepts is used to assign meaning;
- *precising*, whereby a new definition is created by stipulating additional features that increase the precision of an existing definition for some term;

A.2 Creating definitions

ISO 704:2022(E) advises to create definitions using a specific form of intensional definition that is a slightly stricter form of the analytical definition described above:

Intensional definitions shall begin by stating the immediate, i.e. closest, *superordinate concept*, followed by the *delimiting characteristic(s)*. (International Organization for Standardization, 2022b, p.33).

Moore (2009) states that over other methods for definition, the analytical method has as main advantage that it provides both the meaning of a term and an analysis of the characteristics of the extension of the

term. Therefore, this type of definition is preferred in this thesis, both for drawing in extant definitions, and for drafting new ones.

I will use the form as recommended by *ISO 704:2022(E)* ([International Organization for Standardization, 2022b](#), ch.6.4) when creating a definition. This entails starting with the definiendum and a colon, then the definiens. Every essential attribute in the definiens will get its own definition, or will have been defined previously, unless I can consider it part of the background knowledge of the reader.

A.3 Criteria with which to evaluate a definition

Selecting a preferred type of definition (here: the analytical type) does not by itself answer the question of how the quality of a definition of such a type can be assessed. But this question is addressed in the work of Saenz et al. (2009), which presents a number of specifications against which a definition of the analytical variety can be validated. These specifications are presented in table 3 below. In this thesis, I will refer to these as *the criteria for definitions*, as I will qualitatively judge new and extant definitions on these criteria.

1. A definition must state essential attributes;
2. A definition must be non-circular;
3. A definition must be accurately scoped;
4. A definition should have clarity;
5. A definition should be affirmative;
6. A definition should be simple.

Table 3: Six criteria for judging the quality of a definition (Saenz et al., 2009, p.488).

Saenz et al. provide clarifications for each of the specifications presented in table 3:

- *Essential attributes* are those considered intrinsic, related to the origin of the term, how it relates to other objects or terms, and how the term is commonly used. Non-essential or collateral attributes, while linked to the essential ones, matter less to the definition itself. Note that for essential attributes themselves, a definition must be available or derived, on which the Saenz specifications can then be recursively applied. This recursion can continue until the definition of such an attribute can safely be judged to be common knowledge for the intended audience of the definition.
- *Non-circular* means that neither the definiendum nor any synonym, antonym or derived term can be part of the definiens.
- The *scope* of a definition refers to how well the definiens actually covers its subject or working area. When a definiens covers more or fewer objects than the definiendum is supposed to cover, then the scope of the definition is too wide or too narrow, respectively. Note that a definition can be both too wide in one respect (including objects under the definition that it should not include), and simultaneously too narrow in another respect (excluding other objects that it should not exclude).
- *Clarity* speaks to the language used in the definiens, requiring the definiens to be literal and unambiguous, not contain obscure or metaphorical language, nor jargon that the audience for the definition is not likely to be familiar with.
- A definition is *affirmative* when the definiens describes what the definiendum *is*, rather than what it *is not*.
- A definition will be *simple*, if it is complete yet concise, using no more words and concepts than necessary – a test of its economy of language.

Note that the analytical method of definition is well suited to comply with the first specification of Saenz et al., as the analytical approach will glean essential attributes from the differentia. Furthermore, the analytical method will make its resulting definiens likely to comply with specifications 2 and 3.

A.4 Testing definitions

The specifications from table 3 can be used to judge the quality of definitions – either extant ones, or proposals for new ones. This procedure has the following form:

1. Check the form of the definition. Ideally, it will have the form: “definiendum: definiens”.
2. Check if the definiens provides essential attributes. Furthermore, for a definition to be considered usable, these essential attributes must themselves be defined, unless their meaning can be considered background knowledge for the intended audience of the definition.
3. Check the definition for circularity. The definiendum must not form a part of the definiens. This includes terms that are some reformulation or synonym for the definiendum. If the definiens depends on (some form of) the definiendum, then the definition itself is unhelpful. But circularity can also occur via the essential attributes: if a fork is defined as an implement with two or more prongs, and a prong is then itself defined as a part of a fork, then this definition is circular.
4. Check if the definition is well scoped. This involves a judgment call on whether the definiens cover all instances of the defined subject, and no more. Note that such a judgment call is hard or impossible when you rely on the definition itself to recognize instances of the definiendum. If instances of the definiendum are available, then it is possible to test the definition by comparing the definiens to such instances. If such a known instance of the definiendum has attributes that conflict with the definiens, then the scope of the definition is wrong.
5. Check if the definition is affirmative. A definition may contain exclusions or negations in order to establish its scope, but it cannot solely or mostly rely on these.
6. Judge the clarity and simplicity of the definition. This entails checking the language used in the definiens against the vocabulary that the intended audience for the definition is likely to have. Furthermore, the definiens should contain as few terms as possible.

The procedure cannot result in objective validation, as it consists of subjective checks on, and judgment of, what is essentially an expression of language. Nevertheless, this procedure provides a repeatable, structured approach to come to a judgment call. Therefore I will in this thesis use this procedure to judge whether a definition validates poorly, fairly, well, or otherwise. Such a judgment will include the degree to which I believe the definition fulfills each of the specifications in this list, and the degree to which essential attributes are sufficiently specified and defined.

A.5 Creating definitions

Based on the preceding sections, I propose the following procedure for creating an analytical definition:

1. Determine/define the audience for which to draft the definition. The intended audience will affect both the language used to draft the definition, and the degree to which essential attributes need to be defined themselves. For good form, ensure that the audience to which the definition is geared is connected with the definition. One way of doing this is by explicitly declaring the intended audience, either near the definition itself, or for the document as a whole.
2. Choose a suitable term for the definiendum. The chosen term should by itself convey to the definition’s audience the meaning of the definiendum as much as possible. In other words, the term should be an appropriate description. Furthermore, the intended audience must not already understand that term in a way that significantly differs from what the new definition attempts to convey. Finally, the intended audience will more readily recognize and accept the chosen term, if

it is already present in their vocabulary. In summary: the term should ideally be not so familiar that the intended audience understands it differently from the definiens, neither so exotic that all or most audience members feel the need to look it up in a comprehensive dictionary.

3. Determine the scope of the definition. It must be clear which objects the definition must cover, and where coverage by the definition must end.
4. Declare the essential attributes. Taken together, these need to clearly cover the intended scope – no more and no less. If the scope of the definition is too wide (overall or in some aspect), then the definiens needs to be expanded with additional essential attributes that help reduce the actual scope towards the intended scope. And if the scope is too narrow (overall or in some aspect), then the essential attributes in the definiens that cause this limitation need to be reformulated or removed.
5. If an essential attribute is in a form that the intended audience may not understand or misunderstand: provide/create a definition for that specific attribute. For this attribute definition, a separate instance of this procedure can be started.
6. Write the definiens as a compact and non-ambiguous statement, containing all its essential attributes. Avoid non-affirmative statements such as negations, as well as insertion of (reformulations of) the definiendum, or synonyms thereof. Ensure the resulting statement is an accurate expression of the intended scope.
7. Refine the definiens as needed to ensure clarity and simplicity. This refining can be performed by means of textual analysis, keeping in mind the anticipated available vocabulary of the target audience.
8. Finally, test the drafted definition using the procedure provided in appendix A.4. If the definition does not validate well, then one or more of the prior steps in this procedure need to be repeated so that validation then succeeds.

In this thesis, new definitions will need to be created for those situations where existing definitions or explanations require redrafted into a definiendum = definiens form, as well as those where wholly new definitions are crafted. In these cases, this procedure will be followed. This ensures that each definition newly drafted in this thesis will validate well against the list of specifications from table 3.

Acronyms

EA	Enterprise Architecture	1, 5, 18, 20, 34, 35, 38, 48
EAM	Enterprise Architecture Model	1, 5, 7, 11, 19, 20, 34, 44, 48
EAMOn	Enterprise Architecture Model Ontology	6–8, 11, 34, 44, 48
EVM	Expected Value of Modeling	17
QA	Quality Attribute	31, 34, 35, 41, 51
RoME	Return on Modeling Effort	2, 5, 12, 17, 36, 52
TOGAF	The Open Group Architecture Framework	3, 19, 35, 38
UFO	Unified Foundational Ontology	2, 6, 8, 44

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Originally my master thesis was intended to directly build upon the bachelor thesis that I completed in 2020. That would have meant taking a closer look at EAM quality attributes than I had done in my bachelor's, formulate a coherent and comprehensive set, and test this thoroughly with the architects and modelers in my network. But as a master thesis requires more scientific rigor, I should first lay down some solid foundations – I thought.

However, after some probing questions of my promotor I found that these foundations were not quite as solid as I thought, and the literature was very sparse where the ontology of EA modeling was concerned. That meant putting substantially more effort into this ontology. But that then turned into actually doing foundational research. I found that exciting! Tough, but exciting!

As I went through building the ontology that would enable my EAM QA research, the size of my ontology chapter ballooned, until it came to the point where my promotor and I concluded that finishing up the ontology section was a full master's thesis workload in and of itself. That is when I shelved the other results and materials I had already compiled, and switched fully to foundational ontology work.

I learned that while you may decide on researching one thing, the research results may bring something quite different.

When finishing up the thesis, I kept on finding statements that could use some extra substantiation. And the more I learned about the different things I was investigating, the more I found myself able to challenge my prior reasoning, which tempted me to look for papers that supported the challenge. In order to actually finish the thesis, three days before the deadline I had to stop myself from trying to find even more literature.

I found out that you are never done researching.

It is unnecessary to state that I now know so much more about my research topic than before I began – that is the whole point of the research. It is utter cliché to even say that I now know how little I know – even though that is true as well. But an insight that I want to share here is this: after finishing my bachelor's thesis, I was pretty pleased with the result, convinced that I had done quite a good job. But when I recently opened up that thesis again to check on some reference, it struck me how much better I could do the same research today, with the lessons learned at Antwerp Management School, and the guidance of my promotor and especially my co-promotor.

I once more feel pretty pleased, this time with my master thesis work. However I do not doubt that in two or three years time, while working on more EAM quality research, I will open up this thesis and see some, or many, aspects that can definitely be improved upon. This reminds me of a very thoughtful maxim written on a building of the Erasmus University in Rotterdam, where I did a stint as ICT architect. It says “De enige manier om beter te worden is je eigen werk afkeuren” – in English: “the only way to improve is to deprecate your own work”. Although I do not think that my previous results are actually bad, or my work on it was substandard. It is just that I believe that I can now do it better.

I believe there is always room to improve; at the same time, the results of the past speak for themselves.